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D6.1 - Guidelines for the usage of components for technical and semantic interoperability in cross-domain use cases

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Lead Author (Org)	Esteban González (UPM)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Bo Nygaard Bai (DTU-DeiC), Fabrice Jouanot (CNRS), Agnes Jasinska (UEDIN/DCC), Lassi Lager (CSC), Vyacheslav Tykhonov (KNAW-DANS), Hilde Orten (SIKT), Benjamin Beuster (SIKT), Nick Juty (UNIMAN), Yann LeFranc (eSDF), Joonas Kesäniemi (CSC), Matti Heikkurinen (CODATA), Simon Hodson (CODATA)
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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
HPC	High-Performance Computing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PHIDIAS	Prototype of HPC/Data Infrastructure for On-demand Services
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SA	Semantic Artefact
SAC	Semantic Artefact Catalogue
MSCR	Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
DTR	Data Type Registry
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit
PID	Persistent Identifier
PIDMR	PID Meta Resolver
RSAC	Research Software APIs and Connectors
RAiD	Research Activity Identifier
RDGraph	Research Discovery Graph
SQAaaS	Software Quality Assurance as a Service
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework
IDDAS	Interdisciplinary Data Discovery and Access Service
EAL	Earth Analytical Lab
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary (W3C standard for describing datasets)
SPARQL	Protocol and query language for RDF (semantic web)
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
SNOMED CT	Systematised Nomenclature of Medicine -- Clinical Terms
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (standard for geospatial data)

Executive Summary

This deliverable, *D6.1 – Guidelines for the usage of components for technical and semantic interoperability in cross-domain use cases*, is produced within the FAIR-IMPACT project under *Work Package 6 Interoperability*. Its central objective is to provide actionable guidance for achieving semantic and technical interoperability in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), especially in the context of cross-domain research and data integration.

Interoperability—defined as the ability of different systems and organisations to work together effectively—is a foundational principle of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) digital objects and critical to the success of EOSC. This report focuses on the two challenging and interdependent dimensions: technical interoperability (concerning data exchange mechanisms, protocols, and system integration) and semantic interoperability (concerning shared understanding of data through vocabularies, ontologies, and metadata).

The deliverable synthesises findings from various sources, including EOSC task force outputs¹, contributions from FAIR-IMPACT work packages (WP3 - PID, WP4 - Metadata and ontologies and WP5 - FAIR Assessment), and evaluation of core EOSC components such as the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), PID Graph, Data Type Registry (DTR), and Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT). It analyses the use of these tools in seven representative cross-domain projects—Aqualnra, Blue-Cloud, EOSC4CANCER, FAIR-EASE, EOSC Future, SciLake, and WorldFAIR—highlighting real-world interoperability challenges and solutions.

Key observations include the ubiquitous need for metadata harmonisation, the importance of crosswalks and mappings, the underutilisation of certain EOSC tools, and the potential of AI-assisted methods for metadata alignment. In response, the deliverable introduces a set of practical metrics and checklists that align with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF) and Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF), supporting both assessment and implementation.

Overall, this deliverable provides a comprehensive guide for improving interoperability across disciplines, enabling more effective data sharing and reuse within EOSC. It emphasises the importance of practical, well-documented solutions and the adoption of common standards, while recognising the evolving role of artificial intelligence in supporting future scalability and automation.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8102786>

1. Introduction

Interoperability – broadly defined as the ability of different systems to exchange information and work together smoothly and without barriers – is fundamental to realising the vision of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as the open web of research data, resources, and services. This open web will foster collaboration, facilitate technological innovation, speed up the scientific discovery process, and accelerate the progress of European research. Interoperability is also a crucial component of the FAIR principles which aim to make research data,² research software,³ and other research outputs (collectively referred to as FAIR Digital Objects or FDOs⁴) Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Following the EOSC Interoperability Framework⁵ (EOSC IF), we distinguish four types of interoperability: **Legal, Organisational, Semantic, and Technical**. This deliverable focuses on the **Semantic** and **Technical** aspects of interoperability. We use the following working definitions for these aspects: *semantic interoperability* allows the precise format and meaning of information to be faithfully preserved and correctly understood during an exchange, while *technical interoperability* allows two different applications or systems to easily and accurately pass information, share protocols, or complete a task.

We concentrate our analysis on the *core EOSC interoperability components*, i.e., tools, applications, and services that, when onboarded into the EOSC, will directly support semantic and technical interoperability within the EOSC. Our particular focus is on the core interoperability components for *cross-domain use cases* and the effective use of these components to enhance semantic and technical interoperability in cross-domain collaboration, resource sharing, and knowledge exchange within the EOSC Federation.⁶

It is worth noting that, in practice, semantic and technical interoperability are often interdependent, i.e., semantic interoperability is often implemented via technical solutions, while technical interoperability relies on semantic interoperability. Furthermore, although not the focus of this deliverable, legal and organisational interoperability are also critical to consider.

The current deliverable is the work of the FAIR-IMPACT⁷ Task (T6.1) on Semantic and Technical Interoperability. The main objective of the task was to identify and analyse interoperability guidelines and applications of these guidelines in specific use cases from various EOSC projects, as well as to examine the role of specific core interoperability components and offer guidance on their effective usage to support semantic and technical interoperability within the EOSC. This included testing⁸ and evaluating the relevant EOSC components in relation to the relevant interoperability guidelines, and in some cases

² FAIR principles for research data: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ FAIR principles for research software: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

⁴ FAIR Digital Object Framework: <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications8020021>

⁵ EOSC Interoperability Framework: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

⁶ EOSC Federation Handbook: <https://zenodo.org/records/14999577>

⁷ FAIR-IMPACT project: <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-workplan>

⁸ FAIR IMPACT WP6 Milestone Report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940164>

reaching out to the development team to request access or gain additional information. The current deliverable presents the results of this work.

This work builds on and complements the work of Tasks 6.2 *Legal and organisational interoperability* and 6.3 *Interoperability within the EOSC ecosystem*. In particular, we want to highlight two published reports. First, with respect to legal and organisational interoperability, the deliverable *D6.3 - MoU and SLA templates for data interoperability* examines how two types of legal documents,⁹ Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and Service Level Agreement (SLA), can promote data interoperability within the EOSC. The second deliverable, *D6.4 - Cross-domain recommendations and feedback for the EOSC Interoperability Framework*,¹⁰ provides an overview and evaluation of several existing interoperability frameworks, ending with recommendations on how to enhance both the effectiveness and the uptake of the EOSC Interoperability Framework. The D6.4 deliverable also summarises the discussions and main takeaways from several workshops organised by the WP6, including an interoperability workshop co-localised with the EOSC Winter School 2025.

In addition, the work of T6.1, including the current deliverable, is informed by the work of several other WPs, and more. Specifically: WP3¹¹ work on Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), including coordination mechanism for EOSC PID service providers, guidelines for end users of PIDs, EOSC PID policy¹², and instruments to support PID uptake; WP4¹³ work on Metadata and Ontologies, including a harmonised use of semantic artefacts in the EOSC, guidelines for the curation of research software metadata, a framework for metadata mappings and crosswalks between semantic artefacts, and use of semantic artefacts within data repositories for better search and indexing; and WP5¹⁴ on Metrics, Certification, and Guidelines, including assessing and improving the FAIRness (including interoperability) of research objects and semantic artefacts, and creating the network of FAIR-enabling repositories, registries, and discovery portals within the EOSC.

Our work has also been guided by several groups and projects external to the FAIR-IMPACT project that aim at identifying challenges and developing solutions for semantic and technical interoperability within EOSC. These external stakeholders and outputs include:

- The EOSC-A Semantic Interoperability Task Force and their recent report¹⁵ on how to develop and implement semantic interoperability recommendations, including semantic specifications and implementation profiles for specific research communities, the Semantic Artefact Catalogue, and the Mapping Repository with FAIR mappings and crosswalks; the report also provides implementation use cases and real-world case studies.

⁹ FAIR-IMPACT WP6 deliverable D6.3: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770711>

¹⁰ FAIR-IMPACT WP6 deliverable D6.4: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111447>

¹¹ FAIR-IMPACT WP3: <https://fair-impact.eu/wp3-persistent-identifiers>

¹² FAIR IMPACT WP3 deliverable D3.8: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11354246>

¹³ FAIR-IMPACT WP4: <https://fair-impact.eu/wp4-metadata-and-ontologies>

¹⁴ FAIR-IMPACT WP5: <https://fair-impact.eu/wp5-metrics-certification-and-guidelines>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843882>

- The Task Force on Technical Interoperability of Data and Services and their two reports: *Design Considerations for Technical Interoperability in EOSC*,¹⁶ and *A landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework - Capabilities and Gaps*.¹⁷
- The EOSC Association Opportunity Area Expert Group 2 (OA2)¹⁸ that has acted as a sounding board and source of additional input for the work of the whole FAIR-IMPACT WP6. The EOSC Winter School joint OA2/TF1/TF3 sessions were especially valuable in the sense.

The structure of this deliverable, *D6.1 - Guidelines for the usage of components for technical and semantic interoperability in cross-domain use cases*, is as follows:

Section 2 describes the evolution of the architecture from the EOSC to the EOSC Federation. This has had a significant impact on the deliverable due to modifications in its components, and consequently, on the guidelines.

Section 3 explores the core EOSC interoperability components developed in EOSC funded projects, with a particular focus on how these components address interoperability and their integration in the EOSC Federation. Even if the specific components are no longer actively maintained, we can assume that, given their crucial role, other tools will serve the same functions to provide similar functionality within the emerging federated EOSC.

Section 4 examines the use of solutions / components to achieve interoperability in a range of different cross-domain use cases identified by the EOSC interoperability task forces and other EOSC-related projects.

Section 5 presents the approach we followed to create the guidelines. The readers (repository managers and data stewards and in general, actors in research data management) will find guidance for the main components used for interoperability, as well as recommendations to enhance component interoperability and apply AI to interoperability solutions. This section is complemented by the guidelines themselves, which are included in the Appendices. It covers aspects of how to create mappings, as well as the potential of the AI application to support users with interoperability problems.

2. Evolution of EOSC Architecture

As stated in EOSC Federation Handbook¹⁹ published in March 2025, the purpose and vision of the EOSC Federation is to deliver *a system-of-systems* in order “to provide Europe’s researchers with the necessary digital resources to conduct research within and across disciplines and borders in accordance with the principles of FAIR data and open science, in a trustworthy and secure environment driven by the scientific communities.” This *system-of-systems* will consist of a federated network of nodes – EOSC Nodes – that will

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8109528>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399710>

¹⁸ <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa2-metadata-ontologies-and-interoperability/>

¹⁹ EOSC Federation Handbook: <https://zenodo.org/records/14999577>

include institutional, regional, national, and European data repositories, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, and other service providers, enrolled into the EOSC as single organisations or consortia of organisations and adhering to the EOSC rules and policies. The target end-users of the EOSC Federation are researchers working at research performing organisations (RPOs) across Europe, as well citizen scientists and researchers in industry.

Figure 1: Before and After - Schematic showing effect of EOSC Federation on research services

Figure 1. Before and After - Schematic showing effect of EOSC Federation on research services

2.1 Relation to cross-domain interoperability

The recent shift in the EOSC architecture towards a federation of national, thematic, and institutional nodes is, in principle, of either limited or of no consequence to cross-domain interoperability. The core interoperability challenges—such as semantic mismatches, heterogeneous metadata, and domain-specific workflows—still persist regardless of the governance model.

However, with each node (national, thematic, institutional) now managing onboarding of services locally, there is:

- A division of labor in service registration and validation.
- Governance flexibility, allowing each node to address the needs of its community.

This decentralisation allows more scalable growth, but also introduces the risk of fragmentation if not properly harmonised.

The federated architecture also opens a new opportunity. Service registration offers a suitable mechanism to associate semantic artefacts with a service and publish them to the federation. Service registration should entail both technical and semantic federation steps so relevant ontologies, controlled vocabularies, metadata schemas, etc. are published along with service descriptions and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). This would have been very difficult with centralised service registration, but in a landscape of nodes, there are more contributors and much closer access to the required local domain knowledge.

In summary, the federated EOSC architecture doesn't change the core interoperability challenges, but it changes who is responsible for tackling them. The increased scale of EOSC enabled by the federated model will also increase the number of resources that should be interoperable. However, federation also opens an opportunity to build semantic integration into the service registration process at each node. EOSC could leverage this by attaching a semantic artefact federation step to the onboarding pipeline, thus elevating the semantic layer to be a first class citizen of the federation.

3. Description and analysis of EOSC components

This section explores the core EOSC interoperability components developed in EOSC funded projects, with a particular focus on how these components address interoperability and their integration in the EOSC Federation. The core interoperability EOSC components have been developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. It should be noted that the components are in various states of maturity at the time of writing.

The **Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)**, **Data Type Registry (DTR)**, and **Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)** have been developed to directly address key recommendations for achieving **cross-domain interoperability** within EOSC. All three of them are presented using the same kind of template/form structure describing their origin (text box metadata), its function (main purpose, summary description and workflow) and including a list of which of the overall EOSC recommendations are addressed by each component.

The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), the Data Type Registry (DTR), and the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) directly address recommendations for cross domain interoperability. For these an analysis of which recommendations are being addressed and how has been made.

Even if the specific components we describe are no longer available, we assume that, given their crucial role, other tools will need to serve the same function and to accomplish the same task within the EOSC.

3.1 Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)

*EOSC Component: Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)*²⁰

*Developed by: FAIRCORE4EOSC*²¹

Core functions: Repository for Schemas and Crosswalks, Tool to maintain crosswalks

PID: <https://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:csc-202503000310893>

Purpose:

The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) is designed to support the **discovery, registration, and management of crosswalks and their source and destination schemas**. It enables communities to document, publish, and share their schemas, and to create corresponding crosswalks that promote interoperability, data integration, and reuse across domains.

Description:

MSCR allows the registration of both source and target schemas, along with crosswalks that describe the semantic mappings of data from one schema to another. It supports versioning for all entries and assigns persistent identifiers (PIDs) to registered and published schemas and crosswalks. Existing PIDs may also be used and will be promoted for referenced entries. Crosswalks maintained outside the registry can be registered by reference, ensuring that the MSCR can accommodate decentralised workflows and federated governance models.

The registry supports a variety of machine-readable schema formats including JSON Schema, XML Schema, CSV, SKOS, OWL, and SHACL. Schemas in unsupported formats can still be registered, accompanied by a human-readable PDF describing the format. Crosswalks are stored in an internal format, and crosswalks in SSSOM format can be imported and further edited using the MSCR. While the MSCR may not parse all formats natively, it maintains the ability to register and track crosswalks regardless of format.

The MSCR includes a Transformation Engine that leverages its internal crosswalk specification to perform data transformations. This engine takes full advantage of the expressiveness and capabilities of the internal representation of mappings. To support interoperability with external tools, crosswalks can be exported into widely used transformation specification formats such as XSLT, RML, or SSSOM. However, due to differences in format expressiveness, not all transformation logic defined in the internal format may be fully preserved in the exported versions.

MSCR includes a governance model with system-level administrators who manage groups, and group administrators who oversee their respective group's entries. The platform provides API key management to support programmatic access and integration. It also interfaces with the Data Type Registry (DTR) to ensure consistent use and interpretation of

²⁰ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

²¹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

data types across registered schemas. Together, these features make the MSCR a flexible and robust tool for managing the complexity of metadata standards and their mappings.

Workflow:

Figure 2 shows the main components of the MSCR. The **Repository** contains Schema A and Schema B. These are loaded as source and target schemas into the **Crosswalk Editor** to create a crosswalk resulting in a mapping from A to B, that is also placed in the repository. The **Transformation Engine** loads the crosswalk to transform data in format A into data in format B.

Figure 2. Figure 2. MSCR Components

EOSC recommendations addressed

- (FAIR-IMPACT) *Mappings and crosswalks registry to support reuse and adoption across domains.* The MSCR is a direct implementation and concretisation of this recommendation.
- (EOSC-IF) *Open Specifications for EOSC Services.* At the time of writing the MSCR exposes a documented but proprietary REST API. It should be considered to adopt an open API specification like OpenAPI.

- (EOSC-IF) *A common security and privacy framework.* The MSCR uses the EOSC Federations Core AAI service.
- (EOSC-IF) *Easy access to data sources available in different formats.* The MSCR enables the registration and creation of crosswalks that facilitates transformation of existing data sources into multiple different formats.
- (EOSC-IF) *Coarse-grained and fine-grained dataset (and other research object) search tools.* Crosswalks can be referenced both as complete mappings but also on the attribute level.
- (EOSC-IF) *A clear EOSC PID policy.* The MSCR repository assigns PID's to schemas and crosswalks.
- (EOSC-IF) *Clear and precise, publicly-available definitions for all concepts, metadata and data schemas.* The MSCR repository contributes with its repository of schemas and crosswalks.
- (EOSC-IF) *Associated documentation for semantic artefacts.* The MSCR promotes detailed documentation of crosswalks in its editor.
- (EOSC-IF) *Repositories of semantic artefacts, rules with a clear governance framework.* The MSCR provides a repository with versioning for schemas and their associated crosswalks.
- (EOSC-IF) *Clear protocols and building blocks for the federation/harvesting of semantic artefacts catalogues.* The MSCR repository should be federated with the EOSC Semantic Artefact Catalogue to ensure broader discoverability, alignment with EOSC-wide semantic interoperability efforts, and reuse of registered schemas and crosswalks across research communities.

3.2 Data Type Registry (DTR)

*EOSC Component: Data Type Registry (DTR)*²²

*Developed by: FAIRCORE4EOSC*²³

Core functions: Repository for Data Types, Governance of Data Type descriptions

PID: Not available

Purpose

The main purpose of the Data Type Registry (DTR) is to provide a centralised, structured, and extensible environment for defining, managing, and sharing data types in EOSC. The purpose

²² <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-data-type-registry-dtr>

²³ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

of having a centralised registry of data type definitions is to enhance interoperability by encouraging the reuse of existing types across scientific domains whenever possible.

Description

The DTR is a key component of the EOSC Interoperability Framework, offering a structured approach to registering and managing data types used in metadata descriptions, scientific datasets, and digital objects. It provides:

- A **graphical user interface (GUI)** to allow users to visually create, browse, and manage types.
- A **REST API** supporting CRUD operations, including batch uploads and programmatic access to data types.
- A **user and group management system**, enabling fine-grained access control over types and collaborative editing.

Types within the DTR can have rich, structured definitions. This includes relationships such as type inheritance (taxonomy), and associations with units of measurement or controlled vocabularies. The DTR supports not only human-readable documentation of data structures but also machine-readable semantics. As an example, the MSCR integrates with the DTR.

The DTR is built on the Cordra²⁴ software, which is a partial implementation of the Digital Object Architecture (DOA),²⁵ making data types available through the Digital Object Interface Protocol (DOIP)²⁶.

An extension of the registry, known as the **TypeAPI**, provides additional functionalities such as **JSON Schema generation** for type definitions, facilitating validation of an object's conformance to a specific type.

The DTR assigns a PID to any published data type in the register ensuring its unambiguous identification. DTR also registers taxonomy components and units of measure to standardise these across the data type descriptions.

Workflow

²⁴ <https://www.cordra.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.dona.net/digitalobjectarchitecture>

²⁶ https://www.dona.net/sites/default/files/2018-11/DOIPv2Spec_1.pdf

Figure 3. An example of how taxonomies of data types and units associated with temperature measurements could be represented and managed using the DTR.

EOSC Recommendations Addressed

- (EOSC-IF) *Open Specifications for EOSC Services*. The DTR exposes its functionality through open API specifications like OpenAPI and the Digital Object Interface Protocol (DOIP).
- (EOSC-IF) *A common security and privacy framework*. Future versions of the DTR will use EOSC Federations Core AAI service.
- (EOSC-IF) *Coarse-grained and fine-grained dataset (and other research object) search tools*. The type Organisation in DTR supports both coarse and fine-grained views through hierarchical structuring (e.g., taxonomies) and inheritance. Broader categories (e.g., “Geospatial Data” or “Temperature Measurement”) can encompass more specific subtypes. Types on all conceptual levels are individually published with a PID.
- (EOSC-IF) *A clear EOSC PID policy*. The DTR assigns PID’s to data types.
- (EOSC-IF) *Clear and precise, publicly-available definitions for all concepts, metadata and data schemas*. The DTR contributes with its repository of data types, taxonomies and units.
- (EOSC-IF) *Associated documentation for semantic artefacts*. The DTR promotes detailed documentation of data types.
- (EOSC-IF) *Repositories of semantic artefacts, rules with a clear governance framework*. The DTR provides a registry for data types with support for role-based access control, enabling the enforcement of governance policies on type creation, modification, and access.
- (EOSC-IF) *Clear protocols and building blocks for the federation/harvesting of semantic artefacts catalogues*. The DTR has a federation API.

- (FAIR-IMPACT) *Data granularity practices. Consider what best serves the needs of potential re-use. The correct data granularity level also depends on the data type at hand.* The DTR publishes data type information for all levels in a type hierarchy.

3.3 Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)

*EOSC Component: Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)*²⁷

*Developed by: FAIRCORE4EOSC*²⁸

Core functions: Systematic scoring of compliance with policies and guidelines.

Purpose

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) is developed to support the systematic and standardised assessment of compliance with policies adopted within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Description

Achieving the EOSC vision of seamless interoperability for FAIR Data and Services relies on the consistent implementation of policies that promote semantic and technical interoperability. Across EOSC and the broader research community, a substantial body of policy recommendations has emerged to guide this effort. The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) provides a structured approach to operationalise these policies.

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) is not only a tool for evaluating compliance but also a framework for designing and formalising policies. It comes equipped with an advanced conceptual model that guides policy makers and stakeholders in structuring and motivating policies from the ground up.

CAT supports the full policy development lifecycle by:

- Providing a systematic method to articulate the motivations and objectives behind a policy.
- Offering a general framework to define principles, translate them into criteria, and specify metrics that enable objective assessment.
- Enabling the use of different rubrics to tailor scoring and evaluation methods according to roles, domains, or implementation settings.

This structured approach ensures that policies are not only clearly articulated, but also measurable, actionable, and adaptable across diverse EOSC contexts. By using CAT to evaluate a service, implementers of EOSC services are equipped with a practical framework

²⁷ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

²⁸ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

to assess and improve their alignment with EOSC policies, thereby contributing to a more interoperable EOSC ecosystem. CAT thus enhances both the quality and the enforceability of EOSC policies.

The CAT tool has been developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and has been used to implement an assessment that addresses compliance with the EOSC PID policy for persistent identifiers.

The CAT provides a very generalised formal approach to turn recommendations into a policy with usable controls and can thus be used broadly to implement compliance controls in relation to any EOSC policy for technical and semantic interoperability.

Workflow

Figure 4. CAT's advanced conceptual model provides a structured framework for formulating policies—linking motivations and objectives to clear criteria and measurable metrics for assessing implementation.

EOSC Recommendations Addressed

- (EOSC-IF) *A clear EOSC PID policy.* The CAT can be used to assess adherence to the EOSC PID Policy.
- (FAIR-IMPACT) *Guidelines applicable to PID Managers.* The 16 guidelines applicable to PID Managers should influence EOSC's PID Policy that is the use-case driving the development of CAT.
- (FAIR-IMPACT) *Include the CAT and KB as part of the onboarding process for PID service providers into EOSC Nodes.* This is a direct recommendation to use CAT as an integral part of the onboarding process for PID service providers in EOSC.

- (FAIR-IMPACT) *The EOSC PID Policy is fundamental for the long-term integration of PIDs across EOSC and should be officially adopted by EOSC.* The first policy to be implemented in CAT and be available for validation using CAT is the EOSC PID Policy.

3.4 PIDGraph

*EOSC Component: **PIDGraph***²⁹

*Developed by: FAIRCORE4EOSC*³⁰

Core functions: A graph database tracking the relations between DOIs and related PIDs

Purpose

The PIDGraph provides a comprehensive graph database of PID connections, interlinking research outputs, contributors, organisations, and other entities in an accessible format that can be used directly as a searchable index or indirectly through other tools as a source for reliable metadata enrichment.

Description

The PIDGraph tool builds a graph describing the known relations between all minted DOI's and known relations to other PID's. The PIDGraph is based on an initial graph generated from the DataCite database that is aggregated and enriched with related metadata obtained from Crossref, ORCID, and other relevant sources of PID metadata. The resulting graph of interrelated PIDs is usable as the basis for other metadata services in the EOSC community. The PIDGraph is available as a full dump in RDF of the entire graph for local processing or embedding in other services. Alternatively, the PIDGraph can be queried through both REST and GraphQL endpoints when an extract of the graph is sufficient for a given use case. The PIDGraph service also has a WebUI for making queries to the graph database.

3.5 Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph)

*EOSC Component: **Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph)***³¹

*Developed by: FAIRCORE4EOSC*³²

Core functions: A knowledge graph of bibliometric metadata enriched by harvesting from the full texts of publications

Purpose

²⁹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-pid-graph-pid-graph>

³⁰ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

³¹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-research-discovery-graph-service-rdgraph>

³² <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

The EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph)³³ is a foundational database that connects research results with their broader scientific context—linking outputs to grants, data sources, organisations, and communities. Its purpose is to support users in uncovering meaningful relationships between research products, thereby fostering transparency, collaboration, and data-driven decision making within the EOSC ecosystem.

Description

The RDGraph is a service that periodically harvests bibliometric metadata and full texts from a range of authoritative repositories. It builds a knowledge graph that maps connections between Research Results, Projects, Data Sources, Organisations, Communities, and other Research Results. The graph is further enriched and integrated with information from registries of grants, research-performing organisations, and other relevant sources. Available full texts are harvested for bibliometric data to further enrich the graph. This graph is further enhanced with various impact metrics to provide insights into the reach and significance of specific research outputs.

The final graph is accessible via the RDGraph Data Service API, enabling automated and programmatic access for integration with other EOSC applications. Additionally, curated access points are provided through the RDGraph Portals, which offer advanced search capabilities to users through a web-UI.

These capabilities include:

- **Bibliometric Searching:** Users can perform detailed searches based on metadata extracted from publications and related outputs.
- **Natural Language (NL)-Based Searching:** This feature leverages a large language model (LLM) to interpret user queries in natural language and translate them into structured queries executed on the underlying database.
- **Impact-Based Searching:** Users can refine their search results using impact metrics, allowing for filtering and sorting based on several indicators such as citations or altmetrics.
- **Community Contextual Searching:** Searches can be scoped within a Community Recommendations Profile (CRP), ensuring that results are filtered to be relevant to a particular field.

3.6 PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR)

*EOSC Component: PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR)*³⁴

³³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11191995>

³⁴ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-pid-meta-resolver-pidmr>

Developed by: FAIRCORE4EOSC³⁵

Core functions: A uniform PID resolver service for diverse PID types

Purpose

The EOSC PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR) is designed to provide a one stop service for the resolution of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) across multiple PID systems.

Description

Resolving PIDs complicated by the multiplicity of PID systems in use (e.g., DOI, URN:NBN). PIDMR addresses this by offering a unified interface that can resolve any PID from the PID providers it knows about. PID providers can register with the PIDMR to become supported.

The PIDMR functions as a generalised resolver that maps PIDs to their corresponding records, metadata, or resources. It supports three primary resolution modes that may not be supported for all PIDs:

- **Landing Page:** Redirects to the PID's landing page.
- **Metadata:** Retrieves metadata associated with the PID.
- **Resource:** Accesses the actual resource linked to the PID.

The PIDMR has a service to identify which of the known PID providers minted a given PID and the resolution modes it supports.

The PIDMR can be used in both automated and manual workflows to resolve Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) across a wide range of types. It supports:

- Programmatic integration via its **OpenAPI-compliant REST API**, suitable for data processing pipelines, applications, and services that require PID resolution at scale.
- Manual use through its **Web UI**, which allows users to input a PID, choose a resolution mode (landing page, metadata, or resource), validate its format, and view supported resolution options.

The PIMR is publicly accessible,³⁶ with additional functionalities available to authenticated users via the EOSC Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (EOSC AAI).

3.7 Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)

³⁵ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

³⁶ <https://pidmr.devel.argo.grnet.gr/>

*EOSC Component: Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)*³⁷

*Developed by: FAIRCORE4EOSC*³⁸

Core functions: PID provider for research activities

Purpose

RAiD is a PID provider for the Research Activity Identifier, minting persistent, globally unique identifiers (PIDs) for research projects.

Description

The RAiD service operates as a dedicated PID provider within the EOSC ecosystem, issuing unique identifiers for research activities. Each RAiD serves as a metadata container, linking a research project to its outputs, contributors, institutions, funding sources, and other related identifiers such as DOIs and ORCID iDs.

RAiD is transitioning to use DataCite DOIs, enabling deeper integration with the global PID infrastructure and becoming part of the PID Graph. This enhances interoperability and supports the broader goal of a connected and traceable research ecosystem.

The RAiD service also provides an OpenAPI-compatible API, allowing for programmatic creation, management, and enrichment of RAiDs and their associated metadata. This supports integration with institutional systems and streamlines workflows across research infrastructures.

3.8 Software Quality Assurance as a Service (SQaaS)

SQaaS (Software Quality Assurance as a Service)³⁹ is a platform that relies on the FAIR E paradigm to promote openness and accessibility in software development, specifically in research environments. It aims to foster quality in research software by aiding researchers to meet good Software Quality Assurance (SQA) practices when writing code. The platform supports SQA criteria for both software and services standards.

SQaaS operates by providing a graphical interface for users to compose Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) pipelines that verify and validate their software. Each stage in the pipeline is contextualised in a specific Software Quality Assurance (SQA) criterion, ensuring that the software meets certain standards.

The SQaaS platform supports both software and services quality criteria, allowing researchers to meet good SQA practices when writing code. This approach promotes the values of openness and accessibility, as embodied by the Open Science paradigm, and aligns with the principles of Software Quality Assurance (SQA) processes.

³⁷ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/research-activity-identifier-service-raid>

³⁸ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

³⁹ <https://digital.csic.es/bitstream/10261/358467/1/software-services.pdf>

The framework of the SQaaS is available.⁴⁰

4. Cross-domain use cases

Section 3 introduced key EOSC interoperability components, focusing on their design and potential to support semantic and technical integration within the EOSC Federation. However, as stated in Section 2.1, interoperability challenges persist despite architectural advances, and are often distributed across multiple levels: technical, semantic, organisational, and legal. These levels, as defined in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF), provide a structured lens for analysing real-world implementation.

In alignment with this framework, Section 4 adopts the EOSC IF's multi-level interoperability model as the guiding structure for analysing a series of cross-domain use cases. Each use case is examined, when possible, through the lens of:

- Technical interoperability, such as standardised APIs, data formats, or infrastructure-level integration;
- Semantic interoperability, such as the alignment of metadata, vocabularies, and ontologies;
- Organisational interoperability, including governance, workflows, and coordination between institutions;
- Legal interoperability, where relevant, especially concerning sensitive data or regulatory barriers.

This structure reflects EOSC IF's recommendation that real-world adoption scenarios should be analysed through these dimensions to ensure alignment across all layers of interoperability.

In addition, while Section 3 focuses on individual components, this section demonstrates how those components are used in combination, often spanning multiple levels of interoperability. For example, the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) addresses semantic issues, while the PID Graph supports both technical and semantic integration, and RAiD introduces organisational identifiers that align stakeholders and activities.

The projects Aqualnra, Blue-Cloud, EOSC4Cancer, FAIR-EASE, EOSC Future, SciLake, and WorldFAIR were selected for their diversity and representativeness across various scientific disciplines, data types, and interoperability challenges. Each project provides concrete and pertinent examples for analysing technical and semantic interoperability issues within the EOSC ecosystem. They highlight both specific challenges and commonalities in interdisciplinary integration, facilitating an evaluation of the effectiveness of technical

⁴⁰ https://docs.sqaas.eosc-synergy.eu/quality_assessment_and_awarding/report

solutions and best practices recommended by the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF) and the Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).⁴¹

The selection also aims at identifying the EOSC components most frequently utilised and those underused despite their potential. This analysis helps identify trends, recurring barriers, and determines whether additional guidelines are necessary to better support the EOSC community in addressing interoperability challenges.

Moreover, it is important to emphasise that each project implements its own specific architecture tailored to its needs, which significantly influences the manner in which interoperability guidelines are applied. This diversity in implementation approaches presents challenges when striving for consistency and comparability across EOSC initiatives.

AquaInfra	https://eosc.eu/eu-project/aquainfra/
Blue-Cloud	https://eosc.eu/eu-project/blue-cloud-2026/
EOSC4Cancer	https://eosc4cancer.eu/
FAIR-EASE	https://fairease.eu/
EOSC Future	https://eoscfuture.eu/
SciLake	https://eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/scilake-project/
WorldFAIR	https://worldfair-project.eu/the-project/

Table 1: Glossary of cross domain use cases weblinks

4.1 AquaInfra

AquaINFRA⁴² aims to create a research infrastructure integrating FAIR multidisciplinary data and services to support marine and freshwater research. Interoperability is at the heart of the project, linking these two historically separate domains.

The interoperability architecture uses services such as Virtual Research Environments (VREs) for data processing and analysis. The main components referenced are EOSC Core (Authentication AAI services and integration with existing resources through the Marketplace) and EOSC Exchange (discovering and accessing data via standardised catalogs).

Use Case 1: Baltic Sea Region - Studying the environmental impacts in the Baltic Sea by analysing data from in situ sensors and satellites to monitor and improve water quality and biodiversity.

Interoperability Issues:

⁴¹ Gregory, A, et al., WorldFAIR (D2.3) Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236871>, now available as the CDIF Book <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html>

⁴² <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/aquainfra/>

- **Technical:** Marine databases use non-harmonised metadata formats, making it complex to search for environmental indicators.
- **Semantic:** Partner infrastructures (HELCOM,⁴³ Copernicus⁴⁴) use different standards.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Integration with OGC⁴⁵ APIs for spatial data access.
- **Semantic:** Adoption of standardised vocabularies to describe environmental variables.

Components:

- MSCR
 - Load descriptions for the used metadata formats into MSCR
 - Use MSCR to create crosswalks between the metadata formats
- DTR
 - Add any missing data type definitions needed by the schema definitions
- Semantic Artefact Catalogue
 - The data types, metadata schemas, and crosswalks should be published

Guidelines:

- Guideline to create FAIR mappings⁴⁶
- Guideline to create a FAIR mapping by using MSCR
- Guideline to add any missing data type definitions in DTR
- Guideline to register schema in semantic artifact catalogues.

Use Case 2: Pan-European Biodiversity - Connecting marine and terrestrial data to create an integrated view of aquatic and terrestrial habitats on a European scale, supporting conservation and sustainable management efforts.

Interoperability Issues:

- **Technical:** Heterogeneity of datasets (geospatial formats vs biological).

⁴³ <https://helcom.fi/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.copernicus.eu/fr>

⁴⁵ <https://ogcapi.ogc.org/>

⁴⁶ Le Franc, Y., GRAU, N., Juty, N., Mejias, G., Reed, P., Ramezani, P., Poveda-Villalon, M., Garijo, D., Goble, C., & van Horik, R. (2025). D4.5 - Guidelines and methodology to create, document and share mappings and crosswalks (V1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111167>

- **Semantic:** Complexity of national regulations on sensitive data.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Use of the future EOSC Node catalogues for data discovery.
- **Semantic:** Creation of interoperable workflows based on metadata descriptions and crosswalks using the EOSC tools
- **Semantic:** Creation of interoperable workflows based on European ontologies (e.g., EUNIS).

Components:

- MSCR to create crosswalks between datasets schemas
- DTR to add any missing data type definitions needed by the schema definitions
- Semantic Artefact Catalogue to find semantic artefact resources such as vocabularies, terminologies and schemes.

Guidelines:

- Guideline to create FAIR mappings⁴⁷
- Guideline to create a FAIR mapping by using MSCR

References: AquaINFRA Deliverable: D2.1 Baseline Architecture.⁴⁸

4.2 Blue-Cloud

Blue-Cloud⁴⁹ is an integrated platform for marine data, aiming to federate diverse infrastructures through a FAIR approach to facilitate multidisciplinary research and improve data access. Blue-Cloud 2026 extends Blue-Cloud capabilities by developing a thematic federation of marine data and services, with a focus on interdisciplinary analysis.

The interoperability architecture is based on the D4Science⁵⁰ platform for hosting virtual laboratories (VLabs). Data integration is managed by the EUDAT B2FIND⁵¹ service to enhance interdisciplinary discoverability. The main EOSC components used are EOSC Core (Integration with B2FIND to expose metadata to the EOSC portal) and EOSC Exchange (Use of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DDAS) to interact with infrastructures).

Blue-Cloud 2026 evolves the D4Science platform to include new analytical services and expand connections with satellite and in situ data. Semantic interoperability relies on advanced standards for marine data, including Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

⁴⁷ *ibid*

⁴⁸ <https://aquainfra.eu/deliverables>

⁴⁹ <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/blue-cloud-2026/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.d4science.org/>

⁵¹ <https://b2find.eudat.eu/dataset/028b919f-2f7a-5971-94ed-726f1094a042>

Collaborations with EOSC projects like FAIR-EASE are developed to enhance data harmonisation.

Use Case 1: Eutrophication Analysis - Analysing pollution sources and eutrophication levels in marine waters to inform environmental policies and promote sustainable management of coastal ecosystems.

Problems:

- **Technical:** Time series from in situ sensors and satellite observations are not aligned.
- **Semantic:** Difficulty in integrating metadata from Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs⁵²).

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Improved compatibility via the EOSC Data Discovery and Access Service (DDAS).
- **Semantic:** Alignment of metadata with GEOSS⁵³ standards.

Use Case 2: Global Fisheries Atlas - Aggregating data on fish catches and fish stocks into a single platform to monitor marine resources and support informed policy decisions.

Problems:

- **Technical:** Difficulty in aggregating socio-economic and biological data.
- **Semantic:** Incompatibilities in the classification of species and fish stocks.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Use of the Blue-Cloud VRE⁵⁴ to aggregate and visualise multi-source data.
- **Semantic:** Creation of an integrated database for species classifications.
- **Organisational:** Collaboration with agencies such as ICES⁵⁵ and FAO.⁵⁶

Use Case 3 (Blue-Cloud 2026): Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) - Creating a sophisticated digital model of the oceans, integrating multi-source data (satellites, in situ, climate models) to simulate scenarios such as climate change impacts, sea level rise, or marine habitat degradation.

Interoperability Problem:

- **Technical:** Difficulty in synchronising near-real-time data from various sources (terrestrial observation, bathymetric data, etc.).

⁵² <https://gooscean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>

⁵³ <https://old.earthobservations.org/geoss.php>

⁵⁴ <https://blue-cloud.org/blue-cloud-virtual-research-environment>

⁵⁵ <https://peche.ifremer.fr/Glossaire/Glossaire/CIEM-ICES>

⁵⁶ <https://www.fao.org/about/who-we-are/fr/>

- **Semantic:** Disparate standards for Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).
- **Organisational:** Lack of systematic collaboration between marine and climate infrastructures.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Use of the D4Science platform to centralise real-time data streams. Deployment of optimised algorithms for multi-source data processing.
- **Semantic:** Aligning EOVs with OGC standards to ensure a uniform description of oceanic variables.
- **Organisational:** Collaboration with partners from related projects like ILIAD⁵⁷ and SeaDataNet⁵⁸ to ensure data flow and methodological consistency.

References: Blue-Cloud Deliverable: D2.7 Blue-Cloud Architecture Release;⁵⁹ D4Science Infrastructure Overview.⁶⁰

4.3 EOSC4CANCER

EOSC4CANCER⁶¹ aims to improve the interoperability of cancer research data through Europe by integrating diverse data sources across various domains, including clinical, genomic, imaging, and registry data.

The interoperability architecture uses APIs to connect clinical databases to the Molecular Tumor Board Portal (MTBP) and relies on standardised data models for inclusion/exclusion criteria in clinical trials. The EOSC components used are EOSC Core (Integration services for clinical trial metadata) and EOSC Exchange (TrialMatchAI⁶² platform for patient-trial data integration). EOSC4Cancer employs several integrated tools from **FAIRCORE4EOSC**. **MSCR** Aligns metadata from clinical, genomic, and imaging datasets, enabling unified data discovery and access. **PIDGraph** Links related datasets (e.g., a patient's clinical data with their genomic data) to support comprehensive analysis. **DTR** Standardises data types across clinical and research datasets, facilitating interoperability. **RAiD** Tracks and links various research activities and datasets within the project.

Use Case 1: Precision Medicine for Clinical Trials - Using genomic and clinical data to automatically match cancer patients with the most appropriate clinical trials, thereby accelerating access to treatment.

⁵⁷ <https://ocean-twin.eu/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.seadatanet.org/>

⁵⁹ Schaap, D., Pagano, P., Assante, M., Leonardo, C., Thijssen, P., Boldrini, E., Buurman, M., Antonio, M., Ariyo, C., Maudire, G., & Nys, C. (2021). D2.7 Blue Cloud Architecture (Release 2) (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334925>

⁶⁰ <https://blue-cloud.org/e-infrastructures/d4science>

⁶¹ <https://eosc4cancer.eu/>

⁶² <https://bordeaux-bioinformatics.fr/trialmatchai-a-new-approach-to-matching-cancer-patients-with-clinical-trials-based-on-large-language-models-llms/>

Interoperability Issues:

- **Technical:** Inconsistencies between inclusion/exclusion criteria in trial databases.
- **Semantic:** Genomic patient data is not efficiently integrated.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** TrialMatchAI uses dedicated APIs to connect trial databases with genomic data.
- **Semantic:** Standardisation of trial criteria through models aligned with FHIR⁶³ (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources).
- **Organisational:** Creation of a European framework for clinical data management.

Use Case 2: Clinical Data Management - Centralising and harmonising clinical and genomic patient data in clinical decision support systems to improve diagnostic and treatment precision.

Problems:

- **Semantic:** Hospital systems use incompatible proprietary standards.
- **Legal:** Confidentiality constraints for patient data sharing.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Integration of EOSC Core tools for user authentication and data tracking.
- **Semantic:** Harmonisation of data models with international standards such as SNOMED CT.⁶⁴
- **Legal:** GDPR compliance through data anonymisation.

References: EOSC4Cancer Deliverable: D3.1 Molecular Tumor Board Portal Interoperability,⁶⁵ FAIRCORE4EOSC⁶⁶ Components.

4.4 FAIR-EASE

The FAIR-EASE⁶⁷ project is dedicated to developing integrated services for Earth system observation and modeling, focusing on enhancing **cross-domain interoperability** among diverse data sources such as satellite observations, in-situ measurements, and environmental models. This initiative aims to facilitate multidisciplinary research by addressing the challenges associated with integrating data across various scientific domains.

⁶³ https://ecqi.healthit.gov/fhir?qt-tabs_fhir=about

⁶⁴ <https://www.snomed.org/>

⁶⁵ Nikolski, M., & Tamborero, D. (2024). D3.1 Molecular Tumour Board Portal Interoperability. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11501967>

⁶⁶ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

⁶⁷ <https://fairease.eu/>

Project is using EOSC tools such as the Interdisciplinary Data Discovery and Access Service (IDDAS) and the Earth Analytical Lab (EAL). These services facilitate the management and analysis of large volumes of interoperable data. The EOSC components used within this project include EOSC Core (PIDs), EOSC Exchange, and FAIRMetrics. FAIRCORE4EOSC components are used as MSCR and PIDGraph.

Use Case 1: Coastal Water Dynamics - Studying river water flows and their impact on coastal ecosystems.

Interoperability Issues:

- **Technical:** Non-standardised access to hydrological and climate datasets.
- **Semantic:** Alignment of metadata between terrestrial and marine infrastructures.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** IDDAS services to provide spatio-temporal filters and SPARQL APIs for searches. Use of the Data Catalogue Service (EOSC Marketplace) to search for data and SPARQL APIs.
- **Semantic:** Use of DCAT, a harmonised metadata model. Deployment of FAIRDataPoints to structure data. A FAIR Data Point is a metadata service that exposes information about digital objects using standards such as the Data Catalog Vocabulary⁶⁸ (DCAT) and the Linked Data Platform⁶⁹ (LDP) to ensure metadata interoperability.

Use Case 2: Ocean Biogeochemical Observations - Monitoring key ocean biogeochemical variables (via Argo and Copernicus systems).

Interoperability Issues:

- **Technical:** Disparate data formats (NetCDF, CSV).
- **Semantic:** Variability in biogeochemical data models.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Deployment of a data federation system using the Uniform Data Access Layer⁷⁰ (UDAL). Implementation of a registry based on FAIRAssist⁷¹ to help harmonise data streams. FAIRAssist, proposed by FAIRsharing, is a tool to discover resources such as data standards and metadata to ensure compliance with FAIR principles.
- **Semantic:** Standardisation through spatial object catalogs like STAC. Data integration via PID Graph to track and link research objects.

⁶⁸ <https://doc.data.gouv.fr/moissonnage/dcat/>

⁶⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/ldp/>

⁷⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/84132-development-of-unified-data-access-layer>

⁷¹ <https://fairassist.org/#/>

References: FAIR-EASE Deliverable: D2.4 FAIR-EASE Data Discovery and Access Service - First Release;⁷² FAIR-EASE Deliverable: D4.3 Status and Expectations of the FAIR-EASE Data Lake.⁷³

4.5 EOSC Future

EOSC Future⁷⁴ aimed to develop an integrated digital research environment to provide researchers with simplified access to data, tools, and services across Europe. The EOSC components used include EOSC AAI (secure access), PID Graph (linking digital objects interoperably), and the EOSC catalog (referencing). EOSC Future works closely with FAIRCORE4EOSC to integrate these new components into the EOSC infrastructure. This collaboration aims to ensure that the developed services and tools meet researchers' needs and support broad adoption across different scientific disciplines. For example, specific use cases—such as those in the fields of climate change and social sciences—are used to test and refine the components to ensure their relevance and effectiveness.

Use Case 1: Climate Data Service Integration - Allowing researchers to access climate data across different sources (e.g., Copernicus, ERA5).

Interoperability Issues:

- **Technical:** Heterogeneous data formats between systems.
- **Semantic:** Incompatible metadata models.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Standardisation of data formats via NetCDF and CSV. Development of interoperable APIs to access multiple sources.
- **Semantic:** Harmonisation of metadata models using DCAT-AP. Vocabulary mapping using semantic tools like SKOS.

Use Case 2: Collaborative Biomedical Research Platform - Sharing data and workflows to accelerate medical research.

Interoperability Issues:

- **Technical:** Integration of platforms with different APIs.
- **Organisational:** Divergent data-sharing policies.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Standardisation of APIs for biomedical tools based on FHIR. Integration of platforms via PID Graph to link data and digital objects.

⁷² KRIJGER, T., & THIJSE, P. (2024). FAIR-EASE D2.4 Data Discovery and Access Services - First Release. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13165587>

⁷³ PORTER, M. (2024). FAIR-EASE - D4.3 Status and expectations of the FAIR-EASE data lake. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13933551>

⁷⁴ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

- **Organisational:** Harmonisation of data-sharing policies via EOSC guidelines. Encouraging institutions to adopt open licenses like Creative Commons.

References: EOSC Future Deliverable: Monitoring Framework.⁷⁵

4.6 SciLake

SciLake⁷⁶ proposes a Scientific Lake structured around Scientific Knowledge Graphs⁷⁷ (SKGs) to connect data and provide advanced analytical tools that facilitate reproducibility and navigation through complex data. This ecosystem aims to address challenges related to the fragmentation and heterogeneity of scientific data, thereby enhancing cross-domain interoperability across various scientific disciplines, including neuroscience, cancer research, transportation, and energy. Components from FAIRCORE4EOSC are not directly used but a collaboration exists to define a Scientific Knowledge Graph - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) during a joint session at the EOSC Symposium 2024 .

Use Case: Oncology Research - Using SKGs to explore relationships between clinical and biological data.

Interoperability Issues:

- **Semantic:** Alignment of clinical ontologies (e.g., FHIR) with genomic data.
- **Technical:** Difficulty interconnecting relational databases and graphs.

Solutions:

- **Semantic:** Development of the SHINER tool to resolve alignment issues and use the EOSC PID Graph to link publications, clinical trials, and biological data.
- **Technical:** Creation of a data navigation platform SciLake Catalogue. This catalog serves as a centralised access point to discover and explore Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). Deployment of GraphAlg, an optimised language for advanced graph analysis.

References: SciLake Deliverable: D2.1 Initial version of Scientific Lake Service⁷⁸.

⁷⁵ Gareth O'Neill. (2022). Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC (Version V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7410762>

⁷⁶ <https://eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/scilake-project/>

⁷⁷ <https://scilake.eu/survey-results-insights-into-the-potential-of-scientific-knowledge-graphs>

⁷⁸ Yakovets, N., Wu, Y., & de Graaf, D. (2024). SciLake Deliverable D2.1: Initial version of the Scientific Lake service. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12799953>

4.7 WorldFAIR

The WorldFAIR⁷⁹ project aims to produce recommendations, interoperability frameworks, and guidelines for FAIR data assessment. WorldFair promotes collaboration with international organisations to align FAIR practices, such as CODATA⁸⁰ and RDA,⁸¹ develop unified frameworks for interdisciplinary metadata, and create tools and training to raise awareness within the scientific community. The EOSC components implemented include EOSC PID Graph, Metadata Schema & Crosswalk Registry, and EOSC Marketplace. The project philosophy considers that the future of cross-domain interoperability lies in embracing the original vision of the web and using generic, domain- and community-neutral conventions. To address these challenges, WorldFAIR has developed the **Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)** which provides a set of guidelines and best practices for using domain-agnostic standards to support the interoperability and reusability of FAIR data across different domains and institutions.

Use Case: Ocean Data - This use case focuses on the UNESCO Ocean Data and Information System⁸² (ODIS) (and Ocean InfoHub). ODIS is a web-based ecosystem where a global community of organisations shares and exchanges their (meta)data to better understand and steward the ocean using linked open data principles and web architectural principles. The cross-domain interoperability of ODIS is demonstrated through several examples: Oceans and Cultural Heritage, Oceans and Biodiversity, Oceans and Disaster Risk Reduction, Oceans and Chemistry.

Interoperability Issues:

- **Technical & Semantic:** Disparities in metadata structures and vocabularies.
- **Organisational:** Divergent national policies on sharing sensitive data.

Solutions:

- **Technical:** Normalisation of data formats via Darwin Core.⁸³ Integration of metadata into EOSC services accessible via the EOSC Marketplace Catalog.
- **Semantic:** Development of interoperability frameworks based on DCAT and schema.org. Creation of mapping tools to convert and align metadata models across disciplines.
- **Organisational:** Development of common protocols to harmonise sharing practices across nations. Adoption of open licenses (e.g., Open Data Commons).

⁷⁹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/the-project/>

⁸⁰ <https://codata.org/>

⁸¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁸² <https://odis.org/>

⁸³ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

References: WorldFAIR Deliverable D11.3 - Ocean Science and Sustainable Development Demonstration.⁸⁴

4.8 Conclusions

The analysis of the selected projects' use cases reveals several significant insights. The most frequently encountered interoperability issues involve heterogeneity of metadata formats and models, semantic incompatibilities resulting from diverse vocabularies and standards, and organisational challenges stemming from varying national or community-specific regulations.

Technically, commonly implemented solutions include registries such as the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), the PID Graph for digital object referencing, and semantic catalogues to harmonise vocabularies and schemas. The Data Type Registry (DTR) also plays a critical role in ensuring data-level technical interoperability.

However, some EOSC components such as the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) and the Semantic Artefact Catalogue (SAC), though potentially highly beneficial, remain underused or poorly integrated into existing workflows. This indicates a need for greater awareness and training regarding their practical applications.

Overall, the examined projects largely comply with CDIF and EOSC IF guidelines; nevertheless, practical implementation highlights the necessity of refining these guidelines with concrete examples and specific recommendations. Additional guidelines focusing on interdisciplinary metadata management, mappings and crosswalks, and best practices for semantic artefact publication and management could significantly enhance interoperability within the EOSC community.

Therefore, there is a need for developing resources such as practical guidelines enriched with specific application examples to facilitate the effective adoption of available standards and tools.

5. Guidelines

In the previous sections, we identified: 1) common interoperability issues in use cases from EOSC-related projects, and 2) components that have recently been developed to enhance interoperability within EOSC. In this section and the appendices, we focus on guidelines for using these components in various scenarios. These guidelines are intended for users who want to use these components to address recurring interoperability problems, such as mappings.

During the EOSC Winter School⁸⁵ activities, participants identified solutions to achieve

⁸⁴ Buttigieg, P. L. (2024). WorldFAIR (D11.3) Ocean Science and Sustainable Development Demonstration (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11242798>

⁸⁵ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2025/>

interoperability. Some of these solutions were in the form of interoperability guidelines. The results are shown in the table below.

Name	Problem	Description	Link
RSMD guidelines (Research Software MetaData Guidelines) - FAIR-IMPACT	Lack of community standards around Research Software Metadata	comprehensive set of guidelines aimed at enhancing the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research software artifacts	https://fair-impact.github.io/RSMD-guidelines/
OpenAIRE guidelines (EOSC Guidelines)	normalise bibliographic metadata harvesting from repositories world wide		
SKG-IF	data exchange across scientific knowledge graphs to enable exchange of research entities (data, software, publications, and links) metadata across different sources		https://skg-if.github.io/int-eroperability-framework
Paper "'Be sustainable": EOSC-Life recommendations for implementation of FAIR principles in life science data handling"	Sustainability with or without means for FAIR (and interoperability) by adopting good practices (LS RI communities paper but enough generic to be broadly adoptable)	15 recommendations for research data stakeholders (starting by researchers themselves)	https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/embi.2023115008
EOSC AAI Architecture	How to set up the EOS AAI Federation and requirements for joining	Interoperability guidelines based on the AARC Blueprint Architecture for the EOSC AAI Federation and the requirements for services/nodes to connect to it	https://zenodo.org/records/10379293
EOSC IF guidelines to access and deposit into repositories			https://zenodo.org/records/8318608
RDA National PID Strategies Guide and checklist			https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg/outputs/?output=94446

Table 2. List of guidelines identified during the EOSC Winter School 2025

These guidelines cover multiple themes, ranging from the description of the AAI system to software interoperability.

The EOSC architecture is now in a transition mode to a federation, which implies that most of the guidelines generated are not applicable. For this reason, new developments are being addressed in the project EOSC Beyond to maintain an updated catalogue of guidelines.

An Enriched EOSC Interoperability Framework⁸⁶ was released in Q3 2024, aiming to advance the seamless integration of services and resources within the EOSC ecosystem. This enhanced framework forms a key part of the EOSC Execution Framework, a new core service designed to facilitate the composition of services and resources, as well as the execution of data analysis within the general services of the EOSC Federation. Within this context, the term "resources" includes not only services but also datasets, broadening the scope and potential of interoperable research infrastructures.

One of the main problems being addressed is that current Interoperability Guidelines for services or applications exist primarily as text-based documents, which are not machine-actionable. This limits their usefulness in automated environments and hinders efficient integration.

It is assumed that this issue relates to a specific category in the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub, which lists 27 interoperability guidelines.⁸⁷ These guidelines describe various "islands of interoperability," typically tailored to specific applications, but they do not form a coherent or unified whole, highlighting the need for a more standardised and machine-readable approach to interoperability within EOSC.

This is aligned with Recommendation #1 given in *D6.4 Cross-domain recommendations and feedback for the EOSC Interoperability Framework*.⁸⁸ "Interoperability profiles and guidelines tailored for these different stakeholders should be gathered in a central repository."

Throughout this document, we have identified recurring problems such as heterogeneity in (metadata) schemes and the registration of semantic artefacts. In this section, we will include guidelines for the use of components recently developed in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC, and WorldFAIR (CDIF) projects. These components have been discussed and described in section 2. Based on the components identified in Section 2 and the most common problems outlined in Section 3, we have prepared a set of guidelines, including defined steps, which can be found in the Appendices. The first appendix provides a practical guide for creating interoperable CDIF-compliant metadata from Stata. DDI-CDI (Cross-Domain Integration) is a new standard from the DDI Alliance and is recommended by CDIF for data integration. The DDI-CDI Converter Prototype Application was developed in the WorldFAIR project to demonstrate how DDI-CDI metadata can be generated from STATA and SPSS data. The second appendix introduces the "Practical Mapping Framework," a comprehensive methodology developed under the FAIR-IMPACT project for creating and managing FAIR Mappings. The third appendix is focused on the tool MSCR developed for the

⁸⁶ <https://eosc.eu/roadmap/enriched-eosc-interoperability-framework/>

⁸⁷ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/interoperability>

⁸⁸ Rouchon, O., Heikkurinen, M., Lehtsalu, L., Gonzalez, E., Fink, A. S., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Jasinska, A., Thorpe, D. E., Hodson, S., Gregory, A., Bai, B. N., & Pansanel, J. (2025). D6.4 - Cross-domain recommendations and feedback for the EOSC Interoperability Framework (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111447>

project FAIRCORE4EOSC. It delimitates the advantages of using the tool for different stakeholders. A sequence to create FAIR Mappings is defined, as well as different scenarios where can be applied. The forth appendix is a guideline to enhance the interoperability of the EOSC components, based on the metrics identified in the context of FAIR IMPACT, and generated from the recommendations of the EOSC IF.

As a complement to these guidelines, we have also considered the use of AI to support interoperability tasks. The prototypes developed can be found in Appendices V and VI.

These prototypes cover the use of AI to suggest mappings and crosswalks between metadata schemas and to translate terms across heterogeneous metadata sources.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

The present deliverable has explored the essential role of technical and semantic interoperability in realising the vision of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as an open and federated digital research environment. Through the analysis of EOSC core components, existing frameworks, and a diverse range of cross-domain use cases, we identified common challenges and practical solutions to enhance interoperability across domains and infrastructures.

It is not that surprising that semantic and technical interoperability are deeply interconnected, requiring joint efforts in the adoption of standardised metadata schemas, persistent identifiers, and crosswalks, alongside the deployment of open, machine-actionable services. Projects such as Aqualnra, Blue-Cloud, EOSC4Cancer, FAIR-EASE, EOSC Future, SciLake, and WorldFAIR demonstrated that while significant progress has been made, critical interoperability barriers persist, particularly around metadata heterogeneity, semantic alignment, and organisational constraints.

The analysis highlights that EOSC components like the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), PID Graph, and Data Type Registry (DTR) are pivotal in promoting interoperability. However, tools such as the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) and Semantic Artefact Catalogue (SAC) remain underutilised, indicating the need for broader dissemination, training, and integration into project workflows.

Furthermore, the deliverable underscores the necessity of complementing existing interoperability guidelines with detailed, practical examples and metrics that allow clear assessment and monitoring of interoperability readiness. The proposed checklist-based metrics offer a concrete pathway to guide developers, service providers, and research infrastructures towards more consistent and measurable interoperability practices aligned with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF) and the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).

Finally, emerging approaches such as AI-assisted metadata mapping (Appendix V) and the use of Knowledge Graphs (Appendix VI) demonstrate promising potential to automate and scale interoperability efforts. However, human validation remains crucial to ensure quality and reliability. Ongoing work should continue to focus on the harmonisation of practices, the development of governance frameworks for semantic artefacts, and the operationalisation of AI solutions to support the FAIR principles at scale.

In conclusion, achieving sustainable interoperability across the EOSC ecosystem requires a combination of technical innovation, community-driven guidelines, and coordinated adoption of shared tools and standards. The work presented in this deliverable offers actionable guidance to advance this objective, contributing towards a more integrated, FAIR, and open European research environment.

7. Appendices

Appendix I

Guideline to create CDIF-compliant metadata as DDI-CDI

DDI-Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI)⁸⁹ is a free and open structural metadata standard modeled in the Unified Modeling Language (UML),⁹⁰ and is the latest product of the DDI Alliance.⁹¹ In particular, it provides descriptions of data structure and a mechanism for linking conceptual definitions of variables with their implementation (the variable cascade). Each of these components is valuable when decomposing and recomposing data: consequently, DDI-CDI is recommended by CDIF for data integration.

The DDI-CDI Converter Prototype Application is a web-based tool that allows users to convert metadata on variable and observation (instance value) levels from rectangular (wide format) data files in the proprietary data formats SPSS⁹² and Stata⁹³ in addition to CSV to standard interoperable JSON-LD⁹⁴ representations of the DDI metadata standard.

In the following we demonstrate the practical use of the tool on example data in SPSS format, resulting from EOSC Future's cross-disciplinary Science Project 'Climate Neutral and Smart Cities'.⁹⁵

In this project, data from the European Social Survey (ESS)⁹⁶ for a selection of larger European cities were enriched by a set of climate related indicators based on data from Copernicus ERA5⁹⁷ and air quality indicators, based on data from the European Environmental Agency (EEA).⁹⁸ Social scientists and environmental specialists worked together to produce a set of indicator variables that matched the ESS data on topic, time and geography.

Challenges

One of the challenges in the 'Climate Neutral and Smart Cities' Science Project was to find machine readable metadata on the variable level for the data downloaded from the Copernicus ERA5 and EEA websites.

Copernicus ERA5 provides data files containing minimal structural metadata. Comprehensive variable lists with definition, and rich quality assessment documentation (re-analyses

⁸⁹ <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-cdi>

⁹⁰ <https://www.uml.org/>

⁹¹ <https://ddialliance.org/>

⁹² <https://www.ibm.com/products/spss-statistics>

⁹³ <https://www.stata.com/>

⁹⁴ <https://json-ld.org/>

⁹⁵ <https://eoscfuture.eu/data/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities/>

⁹⁶ <https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/>

⁹⁷ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

⁹⁸ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en>

methods, validations etc) can be found on the web site. The website also contains technical documentation about provenance and geospatial aspects of data.

For the EEA, metadata is available as .csv with links to vocabularies and related concepts (through EIONET⁹⁹), while variable lists and data related documentation is available from the web-site. Measurement stations are well documented in the metadata. The web-site also provides links to topic pages and related reports.

For the ESS, however, detailed study and variable level metadata is structured in the DDI-Lifecycle standard. Methods and processes information is, however, only available in documents. In the Science Project the ESS Data Portal was used for the publication of data. Metadata for the environmental indicators was structured in DDI-Lifecycle¹⁰⁰ in the Colectica tool that the ESS Data Portal is based on.

Still, from the perspective of cross-domain use-case, DDI-CDI is a better fit for our purposes, due to its level of granularity when it comes to covering observation level metadata, multiple data structures and its ability to connect to other standards.

From proprietary data formats to open cross-domain standards

In this use-case we start by downloading the integrated dataset 'merged-EOSC-ESS8e02_2', edition 1.0, in SPSS from the ESS Data Portal. This data set contains data from the ESS round 8 rotating questionnaire module about climate change, in addition to other ESS variables. The data is also enriched with the set of climate related indicators like temperature, precipitation and wind, and classical quality indicators like PM10, PM2,5, SO2 etc., all for a selection of ten larger European cities.

The DDI-CDI converter prototype application, developed first under the WorldFAIR project (version 1) and improved in FAIR-IMPACT (version 2), is designed to convert data in SPSS and STATA formats to the JSON-LD representation of the open metadata standard DDI-CDI. Proprietary data formats like SPSS and STATA are primarily created to facilitate statistical analyses, and often carry a licence that involves payment, and thus not accessible to all. However, open metadata standard formats like DDI-CDI allows the structuring of data and metadata in interoperable formats for integration and reuse and can easily be imported into any application accepting the same DDI-CDI profile.

Step 1: Import the data file

We start by uploading the 'merged-EOSC-ESS8e02_2', edition 1.0' SPSS data file to the tool using the 'Select a File' option.

⁹⁹ <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-lifecycle>

Figure 5. Selection of data file

Step 2: Explore data file

When the data file has been uploaded to the tool we can start to explore the content. From the **data view** we can view the column headers that represent the variables, as well as the data values for the five first rows in the data file.

name	essround	edition	proddate	idno	cntry	dweight	pspwght	pweight	anweight	nwspol	netusoft
ESS8e02_2	8	2.2	10.12.2020	1	AT	0.6116770505905151	1.1784955263137817	0.37039288878440857	0.43650636076927185	120	4
ESS8e02_2	8	2.2	10.12.2020	2	AT	1.2233541011810303	0.8994715213775635	0.37039288878440857	0.33315786719322205	120	5
ESS8e02_2	8	2.2	10.12.2020	6	AT	0.6425939798355103	0.4724673926830292	0.37039288878440857	0.17499856650829315	30	5
ESS8e02_2	8	2.2	10.12.2020	15	AT	1.7849587202072144	0.9975744485855103	0.37039288878440857	0.3694944679737091	60	4
ESS8e02_2	8	2.2	10.12.2020	17	AT	1.055348515510559	0.6911919116973877	0.37039288878440857	0.25601255893707275	90	4

Figure 6. Data view for the file 'merged-EOSC-ESS8e02_2', edition 1.0'

Switching to the **variable view** allows us to explore the metadata related to variables and values in the tool. The 'label' specifies what the variable is intended to be a measurement of. The 'value' column specifies values and concepts of enumerations, and the 'missing' column specifies sentinel values.

The air quality and climate related indicator variables can be found at the end of the data file.

Select role	name	format	label	values
Measure	imptun	F1.0	Important to seek fun and things that give pleasure	{1.0: 'Very much like me', 2.0: 'Like me', 3.0: 'Somewhat like me', 4.0: 'A little like me', 5.0: 'Not like me', 6.0: 'Not like me at all', 7.0: 'Refusal', 8.0: 'Don't know', 9.0: 'No answer'}
Measure	interview_date	EDATE10		
Measure	aqiwdpm10	F1.0	Worst air quality index level PM10, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}
Measure	aqiwdpm2_5	F1.0	Worst air quality index level PM2.5, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}
Measure	aqiwdso2	F1.0	Worst air quality index level SO2, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}
Measure	aqiwdno2	F1.0	Worst air quality index level NO2, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}

Figure 7. Variable view for the file, extract

Select role	name	format	label	values	missing
Measure	clmchnng	F1.0	Do you think world's climate is changing	{1.0: 'Definitely changing', 2.0: 'Probably changing', 3.0: 'Probably not changing', 4.0: 'Definitely not changing', 7.0: 'Refusal', 8.0: 'Don't know', 9.0: 'No answer'}	{[1.0: '7.0', 1.0: '7.0'], [1.0: '8.0', 1.0: '8.0'], [1.0: '9.0', 1.0: '9.0']}

Figure 8. Variable information for variable 'clmchnng': Label, values information for the enumeration and sentinel (missing) values etc.

Step 3: Assign variable roles or components

DDI-CDI allows the assigning of roles to variables, a very powerful feature. A user can choose between 'Measure' components, which is the default value in the DDI-CDI converter tool, 'Identifier' components, typically useful for data linkage, and 'Attributes', which relates to attributes to data. Multiple roles are allowed in the tool.

For our dataset, variables like 'Respondents identification number' (idno) is assigned an identifier component, while 'Country' (cntry), 'Region' (region) are assigned both 'Identifier' component and 'Measure' component roles, as they may be used on the one hand as variables for analyses and on the other as key identifiers for combining data from other datasets. Weight variables and administrative variables related to the data file production are assigned 'Attribute' component roles, while 'Date of interview' (interview_date) is assigned both 'Identifier' and 'Attribute' component roles.

Select role	name	format	label	values
Measure	interview_date	EDATE10		
Identifier				
Attribute				
Measure, Identifier	aqiwdpm10	F1.0	Worst air quality index level PM10, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}
Measure, Attribute	aqiwdpm2_5	F1.0	Worst air quality index level PM2.5, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}
Identifier, Attribute	aqiwds02	F1.0	Worst air quality index level SO2, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}
Measure, Identifier, Attribute	aqiwdn02	F1.0	Worst air quality index level NO2, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}
Measure	aqiwdo3	F1.0	Worst air quality index level O3, date	{0.0: 'Good', 1.0: 'Fair', 2.0: 'Moderate', 3.0: 'Poor', 4.0: 'Very Poor', 5.0: 'Extremely poor'}

Figure 9. Variable 'interview_date' is assigned 'Identifier' and 'Attribute' component roles in the DDI-CDI converter tool

The DDI-CDI output from the tool in JSON-LD now also shows that measure components have been changed based on our selection.

```

"@type": "WideDataStructure",
"has_DataStructureComponent": [
  "#identifierComponent-name",
  "#identifierComponent-edition",
  "#identifierComponent-idno",
  "#identifierComponent-cntry",
  "#identifierComponent-region",
  "#identifierComponent-intewde",
  "#attributeComponent-essround",
  "#attributeComponent-dweight",
  "#attributeComponent-pspweight",
  "#attributeComponent-pweight",
  "#attributeComponent-anweight",
  "#attributeComponent-ssround",
  "#attributeComponent-ssweight",
  "#attributeComponent-ssweight",
  "#attributeComponent-ssweight"
]

```

Figure 10. Variable component role changed from default 'Measure' to 'Identifier' and 'Attribute' component for a set of variables

Step 4: Select granularity of output (metadata + data)

The screenshot shows a web interface for viewing JSON-LD data. At the top left, there is a blue button labeled 'JSON-LD'. Below it, a toggle switch is turned on, labeled 'Include data rows (limited to 5 rows by default)'. A yellow warning banner states: 'Warning: For performance reasons, only the first 5 rows will be included in the JSON-LD output.' Below the warning, a JSON-LD document is displayed in a code editor. The JSON-LD document is as follows:

```
{
  "@context": [
    "https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-CDI/1.0/model/encoding/json-ld/ddi-cdi.jsonld",
    {
      "skos": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#"
    }
  ],
  "DDICDIModels": [
    {
      "@id": "#physicalDataSet",
      "@type": "PhysicalDataSet",
      "allowsDuplicates": false,
      "physicalFileName": "merged-E05C-E558e02_2_1_1.sav",
      "correspondsTo_DataSet": "#wideDataSet",
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 11. JSON-LD output, extract.

Integration ready data

Data structured in the JSON-LD representation of DDI-CDI is now available for download in a format that facilitates data and metadata interoperability.

The advantage of using the granular structural standard DDI-CDI to document data across domains allows for addressing commonalities between them, rather than domain specific content like vocabularies and thesauri, with the ability to point to these or reuse them as classifications or code lists within the structure. DDI-CDI handles a set of much used physical data structures (wide, long, multi-dimensional and key value), but the conceptual backbone of the standard remains the same when switching from one data structure to another one, facilitating interoperability and integration with other data.

Appendix II

Guideline to create FAIR Mappings

This guideline describes a practical and generic (or tool agnostic) methodology to create mappings with documented steps (the Practical Mapping Framework¹⁰¹). It is aligned with the technical considerations to make the mappings FAIR, based on the FAIR Mapping recommendations.¹⁰² Both have been developed in FAIR-IMPACT. Together, these provide a practical means to achieve the theoretical and semantic foundation needed to create mappings. These can then be exposed and shared, for example using the MSCR tool. The mapping process framework is expressed as 3 documents:¹⁰³ A diagrammatic representation (Figure X), a spreadsheet (Figure Y, and a guidebook (not shown here)).

Which process to follow for doing and managing mappings?

¹⁰¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15000917>

¹⁰² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15105510>

¹⁰³ <https://zenodo.org/records/15000917>

The Practical Mapping Framework provides a defined process to support communities starting the mapping endeavour and a spreadsheet to guide the mapping process (see Figure 13). This framework is composed of 5 phases: the pre-mapping phase, the mapping phase, the review phase, the publishing phase and the maintenance phase as shown in Figure 12 below.

Figure 12. Practical mapping framework process

Step 1: Define what you want to do, why and how: the pre-mapping phase

This phase lays the foundation of the whole process. At this stage key decisions must be made that will influence or define downstream tasks. It starts with the description of the use-case and generates a protocol document which summarises the decision made in this phase. This results in the documentation of design and implementation decisions, such as definitions of the source, target and the relationships between them, as well as considerations on publication/sharing (for example license).

Step 2: Create the mappings according to the protocol: the mapping phase

This phase is the practical realisation of the mappings and their documentation (metadata). Their creation should follow the decisions in the protocol and in particular the format to represent the mappings. This phase generates an initial mapping file.

Step 3: Evaluate your work: the review phase

During this phase, the initial mapping file should be evaluated by stakeholders who did not participate in the mapping phase. They should assess the quality and applicability of the mappings to the use-case driving this work. This phase is crucial as it can lead either to minor changes of the mapping file or to revise some decisions made in the pre-mapping phase (see feedback pathways illustrated in Figure 12).

Step 4: Publish your mappings: the hosting phase

Once the mapping file has been deemed suitable for the use-case, the mappings must be made available either to the organisation for internal use and reuse or to the global scientific community as a valuable resource. The decision on which level of sharing (local, project-level, institute-level, open) is usually made in the pre-mapping phase, and expressed in the protocol. The publication of the mappings follows that decision i.e. choice of the publication platform (e.g. MSCR, github,...), the licence and access rights.

Step 5: Keep your mappings up-to-date: the maintenance phase

Mappings evolve over time. Through usage, they may need to be updated, refined or even deprecated. This phase implements the decisions and governance mechanisms defined in the pre-mapping phase.

To support the establishment of the process and its implementation, a spreadsheet containing a detailed list of questions that need to be addressed has been created and made publicly available in Zenodo.¹⁰⁴ The spreadsheet is composed of a tab for each phase, containing specific questions to be addressed (see Figure Y), as well as a ‘top sheet’ to record those people who contributed in each phase.

The Practical Mapping Framework has been tested by different communities and has been adopted by the British Oceanographic Data Centre and is currently being tested by the Research Software community to revise the CodeMeta mappings.¹⁰⁵

	Premapping	Mapping	Review	Publishing	Maintenance	Expected values	Example
Date						YYYY-MM-DD	2024-04-30
Participant name*						First name, Last name	Roger Rabbit
Institution* (optional)						text or URI	The University of Manchester
Participant id *						ORCID or ROR	
Participant role (optional)*						text	use case owner
Document location						URI	https://zenodo.org/xyz

Figure 13. Spreadsheet to guide the mapping process

How to make mappings FAIR?

To address this question, a set of 18 recommendations, aligned with the individual FAIR principles has been proposed: 4 generic recommendations and 14 Technical Recommendations. These recommendations are clustered in 4 themes:

- Model and Format
- Metadata
- Persistent Identifier
- Services and API

¹⁰⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/15000917>

¹⁰⁵ <https://github.com/oeg-upm/codemeta-crosswalk-mapping-methodology>

The four generic recommendations are described in the table 1 below.

ID	Recommendation	FAIR principles covered
G-Rec 1	Use a model to represent mappings with explicit links between the mapped entities and metadata for the crosswalk and the individual mappings that can be serialised in various formats	R1, R1.2, R1.3, I1
G-Rec 2	Provide metadata to describe the crosswalks (i.e. set of mappings) and individual mappings	F1, R1, I3
G-Rec 3	Crosswalks (collections of mappings), individual mappings, and their versions must be identified with a Globally Unique Persistent and Resolvable Identifier (GUPRI)	F1
G-Rec 4	Publish your collection of mappings or crosswalks and the associated metadata into a specialised repository such as MSCR that provides access for humans and machines.	F4, A, R

Table 3: Generic recommendations for FAIR Mappings

Each of these recommendations are accompanied with technical recommendations supporting their implementation such as T-Rec 1.1 “Use the SSSOM model to structure and share your mappings”, T-Rec 2.1 “Use the minimum SSSOM metadata schema defined by the FAIR IMPACT project to document mappings and crosswalks”, T-Rec 3.1 “Use web-based GUPRIs that enable the access to the SSSOM mapping metadata and data (e.g. PURL, W3id...)”. These recommendations are published in Zenodo¹⁰⁶ and will be revised through an open consultation in the context of the RDA FAIR Mapping WG.

Although developed separately, these recommendations should be considered as a set of technical guidelines in the pre-mapping phase of the Practical Mapping Framework.

Appendix III

Guideline to create FAIR Mappings using MSCR

The MSCR Registry allows users to search and browse registered schemas and crosswalks with resolvable PIDs. Registered content can also be downloaded for use.

MSCR improves interoperability between resource catalogues and information systems using different metadata schema. It can help users by providing a centralised repository for managing and sharing metadata schemas and crosswalks. This enables users to easily discover, reuse, and build upon existing schema and crosswalk artifacts. The registry's search functionality and PID-based identification make it easier for users to find and access the content they need.

¹⁰⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15105510>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111167>

In summary, MSCR helps manage metadata crosswalks, allowing researchers to easily navigate different software versions. It also provides a shared platform for data policies, enabling policymakers to monitor and align policies across different levels and stakeholders.

The following use case scenarios describe how MSCR may be used in different research roles - how researchers, data stewards, data librarians, repository managers, policy makers and funders may utilise the MSCR tool.

How MSCR can help researchers

1. MSCR allows researchers to select from different metadata crosswalk versions and refer to specific versions using a PID (Persistent Identifier).
2. It also gives an opportunity to easily translate metadata from one schema to another, making it easier to share and process data across different systems and platforms.

For example, in a research department, researchers use a workflow to prepare data after downloading from one or more repositories for further processing. The MSCR can help by providing an easy-to-use GUI for creating crosswalks between metadata schemas, allowing researchers to translate the metadata using artefacts downloadable from the MSCR with existing tools such as XSLT engines to translate into another metadata schema needed by the processing software.

Overall, the MSCR simplifies data interoperability and enables researchers to work more efficiently across different systems and platforms.

How MSCR can help data stewards

As a data steward, MSCR can help in several ways:

1. **Standardisation:** MSCR enables the standardisation of metadata schemas, ensuring that different organisations and researchers use consistent terminology and formats, making it easier to share and integrate data.
2. **Discovery:** By registering their metadata schema, data stewards can facilitate discovery of their datasets by other researchers and organisations, promoting collaboration and reuse of research data.
3. **Validation:** MSCR allows data stewards to validate the mapping of their specific metadata schemas to a generic schema, ensuring that their data is correctly formatted for deposition in data repositories or sharing with others.
4. **Improved interoperability:** By providing a shared registry for metadata schemas, MSCR promotes interoperability between different research communities and organisations, enabling seamless integration of data from various sources.

Overall, MSCR helps data stewards to manage and share research data more effectively by standardising metadata, facilitating discovery, validation, and interoperability.

How MSCR can help data librarians

For data librarians, MSCR offers several benefits.

1. MSCR allows for the creation and registration of metadata schemas and crosswalks, enabling the sharing and reuse of these across different projects and institutions. This can help simplify metadata management and reduce duplication of effort.
2. The API provided by MSCR enables data librarians to automate the conversion of data from one schema to another, which can be particularly useful when working with datasets that require formatting for specific purposes.
3. MSCR also provides a GUI for visually creating crosswalks between metadata schemas, making it easier for data librarians to create and manage these.
4. Additionally, the tool's versioning mechanism ensures that changes to metadata schemas and crosswalks are tracked, allowing for a clear audit trail of updates and modifications.

Overall, MSCR has the potential to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of data librarians in managing and providing access to research data.

How MSCR can help repository managers

For repository managers, MSCR can provide the following benefits:

1. Standardised metadata: MSCR offers standardised metadata formats and guidelines for creating and managing metadata, which can help repository managers to improve data quality and interoperability.
2. Simplified processing: By providing a crosswalk script, crosswalk can be exported in an executable format such as XSLT and RML.
3. Enhanced discovery: MSCR's focus on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles can improve the discoverability of research outputs and facilitate their reuse.

Overall, MSCR appears to be a valuable initiative for repository managers, as it provides tools and services to support the creation, replication, and dissemination of knowledge.

How MSCR can help policy makers

MSCR can help policy makers in the following ways:

1. Provide a shared pool of information on data policies from various stakeholders, including national, funding body, publisher, and organisational levels.
2. Facilitate monitoring of evolving policy landscapes at the institutional and research infrastructure levels, where most research is carried out.
3. Enable policymakers to leverage this shared pool of information for ongoing policy monitoring activities.

How MSCR can help funders

MSCR can help funders by facilitating better interoperability between resource catalogues and information systems using different metadata schemas. By providing an easy-to-use GUI for creating crosswalks, the tool will attract users who currently rely on project-specific solutions. The MSCR also enables operationalising created metadata crosswalks by specific typing of schema attributes using the DTR.

This can benefit funders in several ways.

1. MSCR can improve data sharing and reuse across different projects and organisations, which can lead to more efficient use of resources and better outcomes.
2. MSCR can help ensure that metadata is consistent and standardised, which can reduce errors and improve the accuracy of research findings.
3. The tool can also provide a valuable resource for researchers and developers working on data-intensive projects, which can lead to new discoveries and innovations.

Overall, the MSCR has the potential to make a significant impact on the way funders support research and innovation in the European Union. By providing a platform for creating and sharing metadata schemas and crosswalks, the tool can help to facilitate better collaboration, improve data quality, and drive more effective use of resources.

How to use MSCR?

The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) is a software application that allows users to register and manage semantic artifacts, such as metadata schemas and crosswalks. Users can login and register their own metadata schemas (Figure 14) and crosswalks (Figure 15) in various formats.¹⁰⁷ The MSCR also provides a Crosswalk Editor where users can create mappings between schemas of different formats (Figure 16). Created crosswalks can be downloaded in XSLT,RML and SSOM formats for further use.

¹⁰⁷ <https://cscfi.github.io/mscr-docs/mscr/ui-guide/>

Figure 14. A new schema is uploaded and registered to MSCR in csv format, which is one of the supported schema file formats.

Figura 15. Users may create and register a new crosswalk between newly uploaded or previously existing schemas in MSCR database.

Figure 16. A mapping between two schemas is created by defining relations between concepts in source and target schemas.

Figure 17. In the next phase relation between different concepts of source and target schemas is defined. In this example relation is defined to be an “exact match”

Figure 18. In this example concepts of the source and target schema are not equal (funding / award number) and they are also not defined to be equal in meaning, but “related match”.

Appendix IV

Guideline to enhance the interoperability in EOSC components

In the EOSC IF document, 12 recommendations were identified to improve the interoperability of data and services within the EOSC ecosystem. One of the main criticisms is that these recommendations do not include specific actions for implementation.¹⁰⁸ For this reason, and following the conceptual model provided by CAT, we decided to identify a set of metrics associated with each recommendation.

These metrics aim to provide measurable indicators that can help stakeholders assess progress, identify gaps, and guide practical steps toward implementation. They are modeled as a checklist that can be used to assess each EOSC component, offering a practical tool for evaluating alignment with the interoperability recommendations.

These metrics were presented to the community in the last Synchronisation Workshop,¹⁰⁹ and evaluated by the participants in the Support Action¹¹⁰ (interoperability option) designed for this purpose.

¹⁰⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10874897>

¹⁰⁹ [Synchronisation Force workshop series - 2024 edition | FAIR-IMPACT](#)

¹¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

In the future, these metrics and checklists can be used to assess the compliance of EOSC components with the EOSC Interoperability Policy. Additionally, they will guide developers in incorporating components into EOSC and serve as a collection of good practices.

Technical interoperability

Recommendation #1: Open Specifications for EOSC Services , where available, to ensure technical interoperability when establishing EOSC services.	
Scope	Service
Description	This test is related to the documentation associated with the service, especially with the API endpoint.
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does the service have associated documentation? 2. Is it open? Does it follow the FAIR principles? 3. If an API is being used, is it documented? 4. Is there an open protocol for interacting with it? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You need to create a README file with the documentation. You can find an example in the project EVERSE¹¹¹ 2. Provide clear documentation for using the service 3. Register the service with EOSC Federation 4. Provide the necessary documentation 5. Use data formats with published schemas. Schemas should be published according to EOSC policy. 6. You can use a FAIR assessment tool such as SQAaSS¹¹² or F-UJI¹¹³ to assess the FAIRness of your service. Also, you can find more information about assessments in D5.1¹¹⁴ 7. Use APIs with open and preferably machine-readable specifications, such as OpenAPI Initiative.¹¹⁵ 8. The protocol should be published so everybody can see how it works and adapt their system to it.

Recommendation #2: A common security and privacy framework (including Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure).	
Scope	Service

¹¹¹ [Your tasks: Creating a good README | RSQKit: Research Software Quality Kit](#)

¹¹² <https://sqaas.eosc-synergy.eu>

¹¹³ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

¹¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7784120>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.openapis.org>

Description	This test checks whether an authentication service exists in the system.
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is there a specific authentication protocol implemented such as AAI?¹¹⁶ 2. Is this authentication protocol open? 3. Is there a usage license /Terms of Use? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You have to consider implementing an authentication system if needed. This protocol should be “compatible” with the authentication service of the federation network in order to avoid being authenticated in two different systems. The EOSC Federation uses the AAI service. 2. The protocol of the service should be published so everybody can use it. 3. Services need a Terms of Use document to communicate to users the conditions on which the service can be used. These Terms of Use must be aligned with the Terms of Use established by the EOSC Federation. 4. Use the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)¹¹⁷ to represent information associated with the processing of personal and related data in a machine-readable and interoperable manner.

Recommendation #3: Easy-to-understand Service-Level Agreements for all EOSC resource providers.	
Scope	Service
Description	This test analyses the existence and the features of a SLA.
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is there an SLA (Service Level Agreement) defined for using the service? 2. Is the SLA available and open? 3. Is the payment model clearly defined? 4. Are the technical specifications of the service clear? 5. Is it clear how the support system works? 6. Is there a specific section detailing the limitations and constraints of the service?

¹¹⁶ <https://eosc.eu/task-force-deliverab/eosc-aa-architecture-2022/>

¹¹⁷ <https://dpvcg.org/>

	<p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You can find templates, examples and guidelines of SLAs for data interoperability in D6.3¹¹⁸ 2. Consider to use a self-assessment tool for IT service management maturity
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Recommendation #4: Easy access to data sources available in different formats	
Scope	Service
Description	This test checks the level of difficulty to access to the data provided by the service
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is the data access process documented? 2. Does accessing the data (in general) require authentication? 3. Does the service support more than one data format? 4. Are all data formats open? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use some assessment tools to measure the quality of the access. For example, SQASS / F-UJI.

Recommendation #5: A clear EOSC PID policy.	
Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test analyses if the resources of the service has a PID policy or not
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does your service use resources with a Persistent Identifier (PID)? 2. Is the PID policy available to users? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the EOSC PID policy document D3.X

Semantic interoperability

Recommendation #1: Clear and precise, publicly-available definitions for all concepts, metadata and data schemas.
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¹¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/14770711>

Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test checks whether the resources managed by the service use any kind of semantic artifacts.
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is your metadata publicly available? 2. Are your data schemas publicly available? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Register your SA¹¹⁹ in a SA Catalogue. Check the validity of the schema following these recommendations guideline 4.4¹²⁰ 2. Create a rich description 3. Consider using tools such as MSCR to register the data schema.

Recommendation #2: Semantic artefacts preferably with open licenses.

Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test checks the license of the resources managed by the service.
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do your semantic artifacts use open licenses? 2. If not, is the license documented? Are its terms and restrictions clear? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You can check what license is more suitable to you. You can find some examples or using a wizard like Choose a License¹²¹ 2. Then, you can include the license in the appropriate field as metadata.

Recommendation #3: Associated documentation for semantic artefacts.

Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test checks if there is documentation associated with the semantic artefacts managed by the service.

¹¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14917164>

¹²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/15111167>

¹²¹ <https://choosealicense.com/>

Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are the semantic artifacts documented? 2. Is this documentation publicly available? 3. Is this documentation published in a semantic artifact repository? 4. Do your semantic artifacts include an example of usage? 5. Do they include diagrams to show the relationships between concepts?
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Recommendation #4: Repositories of semantic artefacts, rules with a clear governance framework.

Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test checks the existence of a governance framework for the semantic artifacts managed by the service.
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are your semantic artifacts published in a repository? 2. Does this repository have a defined governance policy? 3. Is it publicly available? <p>Guidance: Check D4.1 Semanti Artifact Lifecycle.</p>

Recommendation #5: A minimum metadata model (and crosswalks) to ease discovery over existing federated research data and metadata.

Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test checks the use of mappings and/or a minimum metadata model.
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are these semantic artifacts registered as mappings? 2. Do your semantic artifacts follow a minimum metadata model? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Best practices are described in the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF). Consider describing your data following CDIF guidelines described in the

	<p>“Checklist to Implement” section:¹²² resourcing/goal definition, determine how to generate CDIF JSON-LD, make metadata records available on the web, create a sitemap and notify metadata aggregators.</p>
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Recommendation #6: Extensibility options to allow for disciplinary metadata.	
Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test checks the use of extensibility options that allow users/researchers to add annotations according to the established practices in their communities.
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Are your semantic artifacts based on a pre-existing model? ● Can your semantic artifacts be adapted to other disciplines by adding annotations?

Recommendation #7: Clear protocols and building blocks for the federation/harvesting of semantic artefacts catalogues.	
Scope	Resources inside the service
Description	This test explores the use of semantic artefacts catalogs
Checklist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can your service interact with semantic artifacts? 2. Is there a protocol for integrating them into your service? 3. Is it publicly available? 4. Does it have a governance policy? 5. Do you use a semantic artifact catalog? <p>Guidance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consider using MOD-API¹²³ to integrate your catalog with other catalogues. The use of MOD-API will allow users to query semantic artefacts in a federation of catalogues.

¹²²

<https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/background/checklistForImplementation.html>

¹²³ <https://zenodo.org/records/12579779>

These metrics have been tested with the EOSC Components identified in section 3. The results are:

As a summary, metrics can be used as:

- 1) A guideline to improve the interoperability of EOSC Components by identifying gaps and areas for improvement across services and infrastructure.
- 2) To assess the EOSC Interoperability Compliance
- 3) A basis for monitoring progress over time in the adoption of interoperability practices
- 4) A support mechanism for decision-making and prioritisation within EOSC-related projects

Appendix V

Prototype 1: AI-assisted mappings and crosswalks between metadata schema

The objective of this prototype is to train AI models to assist users in creating crosswalks between metadata schemas. We focused on crosswalks between CodeMeta, CDIF and WikiData to evaluate the model.

Before training the model, the conversion step is being taken to load field names, their definitions and relationships in the knowledge graph as triples. Training set includes an identifier for each field along with all the related information coming from triples derived from all associated triples, and is being input to create embeddings by using Sentence Transformers¹²⁴ to map fields and their descriptions to the dimensional dense vector space which can be used for semantic search and similarity distance computations. All produced embeddings are being stored in the separate storage called vector store. Depending on the number of fields in the metadata schemes and the size of the training set, Qdrant¹²⁵ vector database can be used for large models and chromadb¹²⁶ database for smaller sets. Over time, as more vector embeddings are created, they can be packaged together and distributed as a standalone AI model dedicated to semantic mappings.

During the metadata alignment process, cosine similarity¹²⁷ is calculated between a field and its description in the original schema and known fields stored in the vector database. The resulting similarity score indicates the closeness of the concepts. By applying a selected threshold, it becomes possible to match and link similar fields. Increasing the threshold improves the precision of matches by requiring a higher degree of similarity. In some cases, this approach selects a few candidates from the list of possible fields, which means that AI-assisted approaches should be taken to help metadata experts in selecting and confirming appropriate mappings.

¹²⁴ <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

¹²⁵ <https://qdrant.tech>

¹²⁶ <https://github.com/chroma-core/chroma>

¹²⁷ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.10984>

Initial results from zero-shot training show that almost all predicted mappings from CodeMeta ontology to WikiData property fields are correct,¹²⁸ and provides significant opportunities for improvement. Despite available opportunities, discrepancies in ontology alignment remain a significant issue when two or more ontologies intended to describe the same or overlapping domains do not match perfectly. More research is needed into how these discrepancies can be resolved, as they take various forms, including naming and structural differences, granularity mismatches, semantic inconsistencies, logical conflicts, and missing concepts or relationships. Analysing relationships in ontology-based knowledge graphs appears to be a promising approach and can be proposed as a direction for future work.

The key differences between ChatGPT, LLaMa, and other popular AI models and frameworks lie in the training process: all vector embeddings are trained on factual sources and can be retrained whenever the underlying schemas change. The commercial frameworks may sometimes generate incorrect or non-existent mappings - often referred to as hallucinations which should be carefully verified after each mapping process.

Another important factor is the cost of training new models. By using local models, it is possible to retrain model embeddings from scratch in just 5-10 minutes on an average computer for around 100 fields defined in a specific schema like CodeMeta. Since all models can also be stored as vector embeddings and distributed with open weights, this approach is well suited for Open Source and Open Data initiatives. It avoids any form of “vendor lock” and allows any interested party to train models on their own schemas."

AI-Assisted Mapping Suggestion API

This tool is an AI-assisted mapping suggestion API designed for easy integration into any metadata workflow or framework, including **MSCR**. It automatically suggests mappings between metadata fields, provides justifications for its choices, and highlights alternative candidate mappings for expert review. With possible integration with MSCR, experts can review AI-generated recommendations, view context and schema information, manually check all suggestions and select the most appropriate mappings.

Example 1

In the example below, the DataCite field **creatorName**¹²⁹ was automatically mapped to the CodeData field **author**.¹³⁰ The tool provided:

- An **explanation** for this mapping decision.
- **Alternative suggestions** for potentially relevant fields.
- **Detailed metadata** for each matched field, including:

¹²⁸ <https://github.com/FAIR-IMPACT/semantic-impact/blob/main/results/codemeta2wiki.json>

¹²⁹ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/creator/#creatorname>

¹³⁰ <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>

- Type
- Version
- Description

This detailed contextual information supports metadata experts in evaluating the appropriateness of suggested mappings and discovering additional possibilities.

The screenshot displays a web-based interface for a metadata mapping service. At the top, there is a table with columns for 'Name' and 'Description'. Below this, a form is shown with a 'question' field (marked as required) containing the text 'The question to ask about CodeMeta properties' and a 'creatorName' field containing 'The full name of the creator'. There are 'Execute' and 'Clear' buttons below the form. The 'Responses' section shows a 'Curl' command, the 'Request URL', and the 'Server response' which is a JSON object containing 'retrieved_facts' and an 'answer' explaining the mapping logic.

Figure 19. First example of the mapper service

Powered by a large language model (LLM), this API understands field semantics even when descriptions or labels differ. It doesn't rely solely on exact string matches — instead, it interprets the context and meaning behind metadata fields to offer accurate mapping suggestions.

Example 2

Even when the field DataCite **creatorName** is described differently (e.g., "Note that the personal name format should be: family, given names), the tool is able to recognise the intended meaning using natural language understanding. It suggests the same core mapping (e.g., to the CodeMeta **author** field) and recommends another set of additional candidate fields for expert review, based on the specific context of the description.

This ensures robustness mappings across metadata standards, languages, and inconsistent documentation, making it a powerful assistant for metadata experts.

Name: question Description: The question to ask about CodeMeta properties

string (query) creatorName Note that the personal name format should be %3A%20family%2C%20given.%20Names%20in%20non-roman%20scripts%20may%20be%20transliterated%20according%20to%20the%20ALA-LC%20tables

Execute Clear

Responses

Curl

```
curl -X 'GET' \
'http://localhost:8102/query?question=%20creatorName%20Note%20that%20the%20personal%20name%20format%20should%20be%3A%20family%2C%20given.%20Names%20in%20non-roman%20scripts%20may%20be%20transliterated%20according%20to%20the%20ALA-LC%20tables' \
-H 'accept: application/json'
```

Request URL

```
http://localhost:8102/query?question=%20creatorName%20Note%20that%20the%20personal%20name%20format%20should%20be%3A%20family%2C%20given.%20Names%20in%20non-roman%20scripts%20may%20be%20transliterated%20according%20to%20the%20ALA-LC%20tables
```

Server response

Code: 200 Details

Response body

```
{
  "retrieved_facts": [
    "Property: publisher, Type: Organization or Person, Version: v2, v3, Description: The publisher of the creative work.",
    "Property: author, Type: Organization or Person, Version: v2, v3, Description: The author of this content or rating. Please note that author is special in that HTML 5 provides a special mechanism for indicating authorship via the rel tag. That is equivalent to this and may be used interchangeably.",
    "Property: editor, Type: Person, Version: v2, v3, Description: Specifies the Person who edited the CreativeWork."
  ],
  "answer": "Based on the provided facts and the request for a 'creatorName' property with a family, given name format, the most relevant property is '**author**'.\n\nHere's the reasoning:\n\n* **author** is specifically defined as 'The author of this content or rating.' This aligns directly with the requirement for a personal name format (family, given).\n\n* While 'publisher' is related to the creator of a work, it's a different concept. 'editor' is also related but focuses on the act of editing, not the original creator.\n\n* The note about HTML 5's 'rel' tag indicates that the 'author' property is the standard way to represent authorship information.\n\nTherefore, 'author' is the most appropriate property to retrieve the 'creatorName' with the specified format."
}
```

Figure 20. Second example of the mapper service

Results: AI-powered vs human¹³¹ CodeMeta¹³² mappings to WikiData

CodeMeta field	WikiData property (AI)	Wikidata (human)	Result
codeRepository	P1324	P1324	Correct
programmingLanguage	P3966, P277	P277	Correct
runtimePlatform	P400, P1414	P400	Correct
targetProduct	P6884, P1056	-	-
operatingSystem	P306	P306	Correct
fileSize	P3575	P3575	Correct
author	P50	P50	Correct
citation	P2860	P2860	Correct
applicationCategory	P4290	-	-
applicationSubCategory	P12238, P404	-	-
downloadUrl	P4945, P1065, P4945	P4945	Correct
memoryRequirements	P12323	-	-

¹³¹ <https://codemeta.github.io/crosswalk/wikidata/>

¹³² <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>

operatingSystem	P306	P306	Correct
permissions	P4967, P7228, P2848	-	-
processorRequirements	P1141	-	-
softwareHelp	P1547, P348	-	-
softwareRequirements	P1547	P1547	Correct
softwareVersion	P4669, P348, P348	P348	Correct
storageRequirements	P2928, P4967	-	-
author	P50, P1628	-	-
citation	P2860, P856, P2860, P7937, P7937, P577, P856, P1433	P2860	Correct
copyrightHolder	P7763	-	-
copyrightYear	P577, P7763	-	-
dateCreated	P585, P571	P571	Correct
dateModified	-	-	-
datePublished	P577	P577	Correct
encoding	P3294, P10, P688, P1629		
fileFormat	P3381, P856, P2701, P856, P7367, P348, P1976, P6153, P3294, P1195, P1065, P7569	P2701	Correct
funder	P3153, P6758, P859	P859	Correct
keywords	P2572, P2354, P921	P921	Correct
license	P275	P275	Correct
producer	P162, P108, P162, P108, P1729, P272, P415	P162	Correct
provider	P176, P175, P162, P1192	P162	Correct
publisher	P108, P123	P123	Correct
sponsor	P859, P2389, P6758, P2828	-	-
isPartOf	P361	P361	Correct
hasPart	P527	P527	Correct
position	P1629, P179, P13359, P1629, P8307, P360	-	-

identifier	P4070, P3153	-	-
sameAs	P2888	P2888	Correct
relatedLink	P1065, P7084, P856	-	-
givenName	P1560, P735	P735	Correct
familyName	P2889, P734	P734	Correct
email	P968, P1817	P968	Correct
affiliation	P1416, P2389, P1416, P69, P69	-	-
name	P735, P2460	-	-
address	P6375	-	-
reviewAspect	P4032	-	-
reviewBody	P4032	-	-
endDate	P582, P585, P1534, P585	-	-
roleName	P2868, P175, P175, P84, P6440, P10527	-	-
startDate	P585, P571, P585	-	-
softwareSuggestions	P3295	-	-
maintainer	P126, P2460, P968, P11266, P1817	-	-
buildInstructions	P2795, P10527	-	-
developmentStatus	P5817	-	-
embargoEndDate	P11140	-	-
funding	P6195, P12526	-	-
referencePublication	P6366, P291	-	-
hasSourceCode	P3295, P2037, P1324	-	-
isSourceCodeOf	P1547, P4290, P3295	-	-

Appendix VI

Prototype 2: AI-assisted translation service

Translating scientific terminology is not a simple task as it demands deep understanding of context, precision, and domain-specific nuance. Literal translations often fail to capture the

exact meaning, especially when terms have different interpretations across disciplines or languages. As a result it's a very expensive process that requires a lot of expert resources.

This challenge was addressed in the Dutch-funded project ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations), where an experimental LLM framework called Everythingdata¹³³ was developed. This AI-powered service supports context-aware translation from English to other languages, guided by metadata and domain knowledge represented by the knowledge graph. Crucially, it provides API based service which can be integrated with annotation tools¹³⁴ to guarantee that all translations can be verified by human experts to ensure they align with the intended scientific meaning.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a translation service. At the top, it says 'GET /translate Translate'. Below this is a 'Parameters' section with a 'Cancel' button. The parameters are listed in a table-like format with 'Name' and 'Description' columns. The parameters are: 'job' (value: 'translate'), 'customquery' (value: 'data management'), 'language' (value: 'en'), 'format' (value: 'json'), and 'context' (value: 'Data management comprises all disciplines r...'). At the bottom, there are 'Execute' and 'Clear' buttons.

Name	Description
job <small>(query)</small>	translate
customquery string <small>(query)</small>	data management
language string <small>(query)</small>	en
format string <small>(query)</small>	json
context string <small>(query)</small>	Data management comprises all disciplines r...

Figure 21. Use of the translator service

The current prototype of the service accepts an input concept along with its description or definition, then generates a structured vocabulary entry with translations of the concept into multiple languages.

The screenshot shows a 'Response body' window with a dark background and white text. It displays a JSON object with translations of 'Data management' into various languages, including English, Dutch, German, French, Spanish, Ukrainian, Russian, Italian, Portuguese, Polish, Czech, Slovak, Greek, Swedish, Norwegian, and Danish. It also includes a 'Short description' and metadata like 'concept', 'md5', 'md5context', and 'lang'.

```
{
  "English": "Data management",
  "Dutch": "Gegevensbeheer",
  "German": "Datenverwaltung",
  "French": "Gestion des donn\u00e9es",
  "Spanish": "Gesti\u00f3n de datos",
  "Ukrainian": "\u041a\u0435\u0440\u0443\u0432\u0430\u043d\u043d\u044f \u0434\u0430\u043d\u043d\u0438",
  "Russian": "\u0423\u043f\u0440\u0430\u0432\u043b\u0435\u043d\u0438\u0435 \u0434\u0430\u043d\u043d\u044b\u043c\u0438",
  "Italian": "Gestione dei dati",
  "Portuguese": "Gest\u00e3o de dados",
  "Polish": "Zar\u017cbdanie danych",
  "Czech": "Spr\u00e1va dat",
  "Slovak": "Spr\u00e1va dat",
  "Greek": "\u0394\u03b9\u03b1\u03c7\u03b5\u03c1\u03b9\u03b1 \u03b2\u03b5\u03b2\u03bf\u03bc\u03b5\u03bd\u03b9\u03c9\u03bd",
  "Swedish": "Databehandling",
  "Norwegian": "Databehandling",
  "Danish": "Databehandling",
  "Short description": "The process of collecting, organizing, storing, and analyzing data in a systematic and efficient manner. It involves the use of various tools and techniques to ensure data quality, security, and accessibility. Data management is essential for making informed decisions and improving business processes.",
  "concept": "data management",
  "md5": "58019a8728b6f5db013df893bc59e74",
  "md5context": "b5c3b547a4ea17bcb3c7e0f49eca3e0a",
  "lang": "it"
}
```

Figure 22. Example of response of the translator service

¹³³ <https://github.com/Dans-labs/everythingdata>

¹³⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/14836298>

These translations are context-sensitive and tailored to reflect how the term is used within a given metadata schema or scientific domain. The output is a vocabulary entry enriched with multilingual labels, definitions, and optionally mapped properties, making it immediately suitable for integration into existing controlled vocabularies or for use in creating new ones. This approach not only improves translation quality but also facilitates the enrichment and harmonisation of metadata standards across languages and infrastructures, ultimately supporting better data discovery, reuse, and interoperability in multilingual research settings.

Supporting non-harmonised interoperability on metadata level

To address non-harmonised interoperability on the metadata level, it is recommended to test a prototype¹³⁵ developed by FAIR-IMPACT to expose relevant metadata at the organisational and object level. New developments in the Artificial Intelligence such as AI-Powered Autonomous Agents will provide an opportunity to improve the machine-actionability of existing schema and crosswalk specifications using tools developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC (FC4E) project, such as the Data Type Registry (DTR), vocabulary service, and Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR).

Here are some steps to solve non-harmonised interoperability on the metadata level which can be automated by AI Agents:

- Harmonise metadata standards and formats using FAIR-IMPACT's guidelines and community practices for creating, sharing, and reusing semantic artefacts.
- Use knowledge representation languages such as RDF, RDFS, and OWL to express metadata in a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language (I1 principle).
- Register or index metadata in searchable resources like MOD and MSCR within EOSC.
- Make metadata available for machine-mediated interpretation using metrics FsF-I1-01M and FsF-I1-02M.
- Ensure transparency and evidence-based decision-making by exposing relevant metadata at the organisational and object level.

¹³⁵ <https://github.com/FAIR-IMPACT/semantic-impact>